

Developing Ontologies of Medical Guidelines for Automated Conversation Summarization

Omar ElAssy, Fabiano Dalpiaz, Sjaak Brinkkemper

Department of Information and Computing Sciences,
Utrecht University, Utrecht, The Netherlands

Utrecht University

Table of Contents

List of Abbreviations	6
1 Introduction and Research Approach	7
1.1 Introduction	7
1.2 Ontology Learning Use Cases.....	8
1.3 Problem Statement	9
1.4 Research Outline	9
1.5 Research Questions	10
1.6 Research Method	11
2 Background and Related Work	13
2.1 Knowledge Representation and Ontologies	13
2.1.1 The Motivation of Semantic Reasoning.....	13
2.1.2 Semantic Frameworks and Standards	14
2.1.3 Ontology Learning and Enrichment	17
2.2 Anatomical Ontologies and Medical Terminologies:	
SNOMED CT	17
2.2.1 SNOMED CT Design	18
2.2.2 SNOMED CT Hierarchies	19
2.3 NHG and FMS Medical Guidelines.....	21
2.4 Automated Medical Consultation Summarization:	
The Care2Report System	22
2.4.1 Introducing Care2Report	22
2.4.2 Care2Report Functional Architecture	23
3 Patient Medical Graph (PMG)	26
3.1 Introducing the Patient Medical Graph	26
3.2 Recurring Example: Otitis Externa Consultation	27
3.3 Analyzing the Patient Medical Graph	28
3.3.1 Patient Anatomy Graph	29
3.3.2 Patient Symptoms Graph	30
3.3.3 Patient Observations Graph	35
3.3.4 Patient Diagnosis Graph	38
3.3.5 Patient Treatment Graph	40
3.4 Formal Representations of the PMG.....	43

4 Method for Medical Ontologies Learning	45
4.1 Process-Deliverable Diagram for Ontology Learning	45
4.2 Applying the PDD to Otitis Externa Guideline	49
4.3 Inclusion of Synonyms	51
4.4 The Care2Report Ontology Research Versions	51
5 Limitations and Future Research	53
5.1 Research Limitations	53
5.2 Future Research	54
References	56
Appendices	61
1 PDD Activities and Concepts	63
2 Otitis Externa Ontology	71
3 Ontology and WebVOWL visualization of Acute Rhinosinusitis	75

List of Figures

1	Stages of the Care2Report pipeline (“Care2Report-Mission”, n.d.)	8
2	Engineering and Design Cycles (Wieringa, 2014)	11
3	RDF Reification	15
4	SNOMED CT Design (“SNOMED CT Basics”, n.d.)	18
5	NHG and FMS guideline hierarchies for the Otitis Externa condition (Google translate: Dutch to English)	22
6	Automated Conversation Summarization Functional Architecture	25
7	Reference Graph for the PMG (Maas et al., 2020)	26
8	The Patient Anatomy Graph (PAG)	31
9	The Patient Symptoms Graph ($PAG + PSG$)	34
10	The Patient Observations Graph ($PAG + POG$)	37
11	The Patient Diagnosis Graph ($PAG + PSG + POG + POG$)	40
12	The Patient Treatment Graph ($PMG = PAG + PSG + POG + PDG$ $+ PTG$)	42
13	General Pattern for Ontology Learning from Guidelines	45
14	PDD of the Ontology Learning Method	46
15	Detailed PDD of the Ontology Learning Method	48
16	WebVOWL Visualization of the Otitis Externa	50
17	WebVOWL Visualization of the Acute Rhinosinusitis Condition	81

List of Tables

2	Sets Required to Define the PMG	43
3	Formal Definitions of the Subgraphs Comprising the PMG	43
4	The Care2Report Ontologies	52
5	PDD Process Activities	67
6	PDD Deliverable Concepts	70

List of Abbreviations

EMR	Electronic Medical Records
ENT	Ear, Nose and Throat
FMS	Federatie Medisch Specialisten (Federation of Medical Specialists)
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
NHG	Nederlands Huisartsen Genootschap (Dutch College of General Practitioners)
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PAG	Patient Anatomy Graph
PDD	Process-Deliverable Diagram
PDG	Patient Diagnosis Graph
PMG	Patient Medical Graph
POG	Patient Observations Graph
PSG	Patient Symptoms Graph
PTG	Patient Treatment Graph
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	RDF Schema
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine - Clinical Terms
SNOP	Structured Nomenclature of Pathology
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol And RDF Query Language
SVG	Scalable Vector Graphics
UML	Unified Modeling Language
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

Chapter 1

Introduction and Research Approach

1.1 Introduction

The automated capturing and summarisation of structured conversations can potentially save time and cost in several domains, especially in domains where dialogues are structured based on predefined guidelines. Medical consultations are a prime example of such structured conversations. They broadly follow a systematic examination of predefined symptoms and observations to diagnose and treat well-defined conditions affecting fixed human anatomy.

The rule-based summarization of conversations grants explainability difficult to achieve in machine learning approaches (Rudin, 2019); and ontologies can be an efficient method for capturing domain guidelines for machine processing in such rule-based applications. Thus, ontologies are valuable tools for storing and representing knowledge as they allow for automated reasoning and reporting. The information extracted from a conversation is matched to the prebuilt ontology to produce a knowledge graph for further processing.

Gruber (1993) defined an ontology as the explicit specification of a conceptualisation. In other words, it is a formal description of the concepts in a domain and the relationships between these concepts. In the context of conversation summarization, the ontology converts the diverse and primarily textual domain knowledge (e.g., human anatomy and medical guidelines) into a fabric of concepts and relationships that can be accessed and processed by machines. For example, physicians summarise medical consultations into an Electronic Medical Records (EMR) report that consists of four main sections: subjective notes by the patient (*symptoms*), objective observations by the physician (*observations*), evaluation of the condition (*diagnosis*), and plan for action (*treatment*) (Cameron & Turtle-Song, 2002). For an effective automated conversation system to provide a similar report, it must be able to differentiate concepts and place them in the correct category (e.g., pain is a symptom). An ontology is the foundational knowledge base that enables the system to do so by providing relationships (either explicit or inferred by ontology reasoning) between the concepts and what they express (the concept of pain is a symptom in the ontology).

The expanding potential of the automated conversation summarization systems in the medical domain and into various fields depends on the readiness of the structured representations of domain-specific knowledge in a machine-understandable format. The formalisation of knowledge representation of any domain begins with

conceptualising the notions, entities and objects of the domain and their relationships (Genesereth & Nilsson, 1987). The explicit specification of this conceptualisation is called an ontology (Gruber, 1993). However, manually building a domain ontology can be time-consuming and error-prone; thus, it should be carried out using systematic *ontology learning*: constructing and integrating a machine-readable semantic-rich ontology (semi-)automatically (Zhou, 2007).

An example of a conversation summarization system that relies on ontologies is the medical consultation summarization system **Care2Report** that aims to provide an automatically generated consultation report for the care providers to review and edit if necessary before uploading to the EMR system (Maas et al., 2020). Care2Report relies on integrating specially developed and already available systems to integrate speech and action recognition with a semantic interpretation of the human anatomy and the relevant medical guidelines (Maas et al., 2020).

1.2 Ontology Learning Use Cases

This thesis researches elements of the second stage of the Care2Report pipeline, formal representation (figure 1). The multimodal data recorded and processed during the medical consultation is formally expressed using a knowledge representation formalism to allow further analysis in later stages.

Fig. 1: Stages of the Care2Report pipeline (“Care2Report-Mission”, n.d.)

The thesis aims to introduce a *framework* for ontology learning in the medical domain consisting of two parts: the notational *model* represented in the Patient Medical Graph (PMG) discussed in Chapter 4 and the procedural *method* outlined in Chapter 5. The framework aims to systematically learn medical ontologies from guidelines to utilize in the medical consultation summarization system. The ontologies learned from medical guidelines in this research provide an example use case to illustrate the framework. However, the use cases are virtually endless as every existing or future guideline from any medical authority can be used to con-

struct an ontology based on this framework and its potential updates, some of which outlined in the future research section at the end of this document.

1.3 Problem Statement

The development of tools and techniques for ontology learning primarily aims to enable the extraction of ontologies from general data corpora as it was, and still is, driven by the necessity of linking either openly available data (e.g., DBpedia (Lehmann et al., 2015)) or corporate-specific business data (e.g. Google Knowledge Graph (Singhal, 2012)).

However, more research is required to develop a framework to enable the systematic representation of **domain guidelines** in machine-processable ontologies. Such research is imperative to enable wider and faster adoption of automated conversation summarization and reporting in various domains. This document aims to develop such a framework (consisting of a notational model and a procedural method) for developing ontologies in the medical domain to support the development and expansion of the automated conversation summarization system Care2Report.

1.4 Research Outline

The research goal is to introduce a framework for developing ontologies based on the human anatomy and the guidelines of the medical domain. The goal is to be achieved by studying ontologies and the available techniques to learn them through a review of the relevant literature and industry tools. The research outcome consists of the two parts of the ontology development framework: the notational side represented in the Patient Medical Graph (PMG) model, and the procedural method expressed in a Process-Deliverable Diagram (PDD) model.

The medical domain knowledge is studied by analysing the terminology provided by the Systematized Nomenclature Of Medicine - Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT), the human anatomical units structure derived from the same SNOMED CT hierarchies, and the medical guidelines provided by the Dutch College of General Practitioners (Nederlands Huisartsen Genootschap - NHG).

For a more precise delineation, the research primarily focuses on the inflammation of the external ear canal (Otitis Externa) as a running example and analyzes the guidelines within the context of the Care2Report system requirements. The sinus inflammation condition known as Acute Rhinosinusitis is also briefly discussed to provide a second example.

Finally, while the research aims to introduce a framework that can eventually be used to (semi-)automate the ontology development process, the framework's validation is executed manually. Different steps of the procedure are candidates for automation, which can be tackled in future research.

1.5 Research Questions

The Care2Report system and any future applications of the automated conversation summarization system rely on the availability of comprehensive domain ontologies. For the Care2Report system, the desired ontology should contain an accurate and stable representation of the human anatomy. It should also contain the medical guidelines of different diseases and conditions to enable the system to differentiate between symptoms, observations, diagnoses, and treatments to fill in the appropriate sections of the standard medical reports.

The first proof of concept and prototype stages of the Care2Report system development relied on manually constructed ontologies of small segments of the human anatomy and a corresponding condition: the inflammation of the external ear canal, also known as "Otitis Externa". This research aims to develop a method to guide the systematic construction of ontologies of human anatomy and all the related medical guidelines for medical consultations. The main research question is: **How to systematically construct ontologies from the human anatomy and medical guidelines?**

The main research question comprises four subquestions. The first two subquestions review the existing literature and techniques for knowledge representation using ontologies to provide a background and a roadmap for subsequent subquestions.

1. **How can ontologies be used to express and query domain knowledge?**
2. **How do the currently available knowledge representation and ontology standards differ?**

The third subquestion investigates and develops the notations to systematically depict the human anatomy and the medical guidelines in a knowledge graph representation: the Patient Medical Graph (PMG).

3. **How to systematically represent medical guidelines for automated reporting?**

Finally, the last subquestion investigates the procedural method perspective of the framework and applies it to learn an ontology of the human anatomy and the guidelines of medical conditions, thus enabling the ontology visualization, and the comparison to a previously manually built ontology.

4. **What are the steps of a systematic *procedure* to develop ontologies from guidelines?**

1.6 Research Method

The research aims to find a method to capture the knowledge in medical guidelines in a machine-processable ontology to enable the automated conversation and reporting system. Accordingly, the design science research, as described by Wieringa (2014), is fitting to conduct the research (figure 2). Different subquestions involve varying research approaches that correspond to different parts of the cycle.

Fig. 2: Engineering and Design Cycles (Wieringa, 2014)

The first two subquestions investigate the problem in its context by investigating both the application domain (the medical domain) and the available solution (ontology standards and ontology learning). The two questions are addressed by studying scientific literature, standards, and technical literature about the existing ontology standards and techniques, and medical guidelines.

The third subquestion contributes to the treatment design by constructing the Patient Medical Graph (PMG) as the notational foundation of the ontology development framework. The last subquestion examines the procedural aspect of developing the framework and contributes to the treatment design phase of the cycle. Finally, a limited validation of the framework is offered by comparing the resulting ontology to manually built ontologies by the Care2Report team.

The research does not encompass the whole engineering cycle (in which the validated treatment is implemented and the implementation is evaluated), as the treatment evaluation chances are restricted because the Care2Report system itself is still under development. A thorough treatment evaluation requires inputs from different stakeholders and evaluating the treatment's ability to satisfy their requirements, which is an opportunity for future research.

Design science research continually iterates over designing an artefact (in the broadest definition, including a method) and evaluating it (Wieringa, 2014). Thus, a central objective of this research document is to elaborate on the steps followed to develop the desired ontologies. The exact process can (and should) be revisited time and again for improvement and application on different use cases for various medical guidelines, including guidelines from other countries. From a research-method perspective, this approach signifies that the research aims to answer the research questions and do so in a step-by-step tutorial manner.

Chapter 2

Background and Related Work

2.1 Knowledge Representation and Ontologies

2.1.1 The Motivation of Semantic Reasoning

The traditional structure of the World Wide Web consisted of interconnected documents with little structure and with the relationship between the entities discussed in those documents *implied* in the documents. In that model, the information is consumed solely by humans who are needed to interpret the various entities' relationships. However, transforming the web to be more processable by machines required a more structured web of data with *explicit* semantics and connections between the data entities themselves; the **Semantic Web** aimed to organize the web content in a meaningful, understandable and machine-processable way (Berners-Lee et al., 2001).

A cornerstone of the semantic web is ontologies: formal, explicit depictions of a shared conceptualization of a domain that enable the definition of a common vocabulary and a structure of the knowledge in this domain (Gruber, 1993). While the semantic web technology as a whole strives to transform any web of data into a web of knowledge, the ontology component aims to structure this knowledge; in this capacity, ontologies enable interoperable semantics in complicated interconnected information systems, they enable systems to share and reason about concepts and the relationships between them using accepted statements that are regarded to be established, also known as axioms (Wong et al., 2012).

Semantic web projects in the form of knowledge graphs were more widely adopted in the industry after Google announced its Google Knowledge Graph to transform searches from only matching text queries to search and link entities (Singhal, 2012). For example, a search for the name of a touristic attraction like the Eiffel Tower will not only return pages that have the string "Eiffel Tower" in them. It will instead return results about Paris, France, other touristic attractions, the architects of the tower, the engineers and contractors who built it, the weather in Paris today, how to get there, and much more. This level of semantic content richness is possible because the search engine does not only see the Eiffel Tower as a string of characters anymore but one of the names of an entity related to all those other entities and concepts. Google Knowledge Graph was soon followed by LinkedIn's knowledge graph (He, 2016), Microsoft's Bing knowledge

graph (Shrivastava, 2017), Amazon Product Graph (Krishnan, 2018), and Uber’s food knowledge graph (Ferras et al., 2018) among many others.

Besides these enterprise-focused knowledge graphs, several prominent open ontologies and knowledge graphs are maintained by volunteers, NGOs or governmental entities. Those open knowledge graphs are either cross-domain, like Wikidata (Vrandečić & Krötzsch, 2014) and DBpedia (Lehmann et al., 2015), or domain-specific like the geographic LinkedGeoData (Stadler et al., 2012), the US Government Linked Open Data (Hendler et al., 2012), and the life science-focused BIO2RDF (Callahan et al., 2013).

The core idea of all these developments is using graphs (in the mathematical sense) to represent data (and potentially knowledge) in an abstracted form using already available data, allowing the reasoning about the semantics of the knowledge using several representation formalisms. One of the crucial ideas addressed in the seminal paper by Berners-Lee et al. (2001) is that the ”*machine agents*” will have the ability to manipulate data and extract knowledge to perform impressive tasks, not because the agents are brilliant AI machines (which can be a greater challenge) but because the semantic web itself is formatted to enable such processing.

Extending the same reasoning to its logical conclusion leads us to understand why the adoption of the semantic representation of knowledge, and ontologies, gained much traction in internal applications that represent a specific body of knowledge in specialized domains. These domains are widely varying from oil and gas exploration (Dalglish, 2016) to genomics research (Köhler et al., 2017), and health care (El-Sappagh et al., 2018). This research document is an attempt to advance this semantic representation of domain knowledge (mainly in the medical domain) to enable the automated conversation summarization as one of the promising applications of the machine-processable knowledge.

2.1.2 Semantic Frameworks and Standards

While a systematic literature review of the field is out of the scope of this research, this section provides a brief narrative explanation of some of the primary standards and frameworks of knowledge representation and ontology learning and processing.

The **Resource Description Framework (RDF)** is a World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) specification that represents a data model to facilitate integration between various data sources by bridging the semantic differences between them, regardless of the structure of the underlying data storage and processing systems or the documents representing the data (Miller, 1998). The RDF data model encodes structured information in a directed labeled graph consisting of unique identifiers for the entities and binary statements between those entities. The source of the

relationship is called the *subject*, the relationship is called the *predicate*, and the destination is the *object* (Decker et al., 2000).

The RDF model distinguishes between identifiable entities with unique resource identifiers URI (*resources*) and simple values: numerical, string, date or otherwise (*literals*). The model also makes use of unnamed resources (*blank nodes*). In an RDF statement, the subject can be either a resource or a blank node, a predicate can only be a resource, and an object can be a resource, a literal or a blank node. Resources are graphically represented as ovals, literals as boxes, and the statement’s predicate as an arch (Hitzler et al., 2009).

While simple statements can easily be represented as triples, the RDF specification enables the standard representation of more elaborate and complex ideas. A simple triple about the year of death of King Arthur would be $\langle \text{kingArthur}, \text{died}, 537 \rangle$. However, suppose we instead want to have a more nuanced discussion about the controversies surrounding the story of the historical figure, and whether he is even real (Higham, 2005). In that case, we might need to use sentences like “Historians believe that King Arthur died in 537”, a statement that can not be represented in a single simple triple. RDF provides a solution in the form of predefined special vocabularies (`rdf:statement`, `rdf:type`, `rdf:subject`, `rdf:predicate`, and `rdf:object`). Using these terms and the concept of blank (unnamed) nodes, we can write RDF statements about RDF statements, also known as *reification* in this context, as illustrated in figure 3.

Fig. 3: RDF Reification

Naturally, the same figure can be also represented in textual triples for machine processing, five triples for the five edges in the graph:

- $\langle \text{historians}, \text{believe}, \text{_:b} \rangle$

- <_:b, rdf:type, rdf:statement>
- <_:b, rdf:subject, kingArthur>
- <_:b, rdf:predicate, died>
- <_:b, rdf:object, “537”>

The graph represented above (using RDF) abstracts data from different sources and links entities identified from these sources with simple binary statements. For example, the resource for King Arthur can be a DBpedia resource ¹ to enrich the graph even more. The RDF triples clearly provide a more machine-processable form of knowledge compared to the original natural language sentence “Historians believe that King Arthur died in 537”; however, the graph does not provide a way to represent and query the data’s semantics and reason about it. For this, several additional enhancements are needed, mainly schema and ontologies.

A semantic *schema* allows for the definition of high-level terms used in a graph. For example, **RDF Schema (RDFS)** is the schema providing vocabulary structures for RDF (Antoniou & Van Harmelen, 2004). RDFS is better understood by examples of some of its most useful axioms:

- **Type propagation** using the vocabulary *rdfs:subClassOf*: The two triples <kingArthur, rdf:type, king> and <king, rdfs:subClassOf, man> enable a machine to reason that <kingArthur, rdf:type, man> which is a considerable leap of reason for machines that do not possess the logical inference capabilities of humans.
- Similarly, **relation propagation** is achieved using *rdfs:subPropertyOf*. For example <kingOf, rdfs:subPropertyOf, monarchOf>.
- **Usage axioms** define the domain (possible subject classes) and range (possible object classes) of a predicate. Through *rdfs:domain* and *rdfs:range*. The three triples <kingArthur, kingOf, Britain> , <kingOf, rdf:domain, man> , and <kingOf, rdf:range, country> will lead the machine to reason that <kingArthur, rdf:type, man> and <Britain, rdf:type, country>.

Ontologies provide even more powerful tools to define reasoning-enabling axioms both domain-independent or domain-specific, as we shall discuss in later sections about medical domain ontologies. Ontologies can also enable quantified statements (e.g., all men are mortal) to augment the graph and enable further knowledge to be deduced (e.g., King Arthur is mortal). One of the most valuable ontology standards in use is the **Web Ontology Language (OWL)** adopted by the W3C and compatible with RDF/RDFS (McGuinness & Van Harmelen, 2004). It provides formal representation and vocabulary definitions for information to be more readily machine-processable. It defines vocabulary to formally represent (in)equality, property and class characteristics, cardinalities, boolean expressions,

¹ http://dbpedia.org/resource/King_Arthur

and more (McGuinness & Van Harmelen, 2004). The value of an ontology depends on the extent to which it is detailed, consistent, broad and agreed upon among practitioners (Hogan et al., 2020).

Another crucial component of the semantic knowledge processing is a standardized means to query the data. The W3C recommended query language compatible with RDF is **SPARQL** (a recursive acronym for SPARQL Protocol And RDF Query Language), which relies on the same graph patterns used by RDF while allowing variable terms to represent the queried entities (Harris et al., 2013).

2.1.3 Ontology Learning and Enrichment

Ontology acquisition encompasses both the manual building of ontologies by domain experts working with ontology experts, which is a costly and time-consuming approach, and ontology learning. Ontology learning is the (semi-)automatic acquisition of ontological knowledge by constructing new ontologies from different data sources, integrating existing ontologies, enriching existing ontologies by new concepts or relations, or resolving inconsistencies in existing ontologies to enable a more reliable use (Zhou, 2007).

The focus of study in computer and information science fields is ontology learning approaches rather than the manual ones (Zhou, 2007). Knowledge bases are created by populating the existing ontologies with relevant instances of information extracted from structured or (more importantly) unstructured data sources (Gruber, 1993); accordingly, an ontology can be viewed as the structured container to be filled with information to convey knowledge to machines (Wong et al., 2012).

Moreover, while ontology learning seeks to extract semantic knowledge in the form of ontologies from various data sources (Zhou, 2007), ontology enrichment can be defined as extending an existing ontology with additional concepts and relationships while avoiding inconsistencies (Petasis et al., 2011). However, the distinction between the two definitions does not carry a practical implication for our purposes as building an ontology is an iterative process that keeps adding new concepts and relationships (enrichment) from different sources. For example, the ontology needed for the Care2Report system is based on an ontology of the human anatomy that is further enriched by the semantic knowledge obtained from guidelines of various diseases and medical conditions.

2.2 Anatomical Ontologies and Medical Terminologies: SNOMED CT

The Structured Nomenclature of Pathology (SNOP) was one of the first prominent clinical terminologies developed in 1965; since then, it went through several iterations and transformations to eventually become the Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine - Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT), and is currently the world's most

extensive clinical terminology system, developed and maintained by SNOMED International, an international non-profit standards development organization (Bodenreider et al., 2018).

This research will use SNOMED CT as the source of the ontology representing the human anatomy. Additionally, SNOMED CT will serve as a terminology hierarchy to identify relevant medical concepts from all the potential concepts in the textual medical guidelines (Chapter 4).

2.2.1 SNOMED CT Design

An overview of the design of SNOMED CT (figure 4) guides the user’s understanding of its components (“SNOMED CT Basics”, n.d.). The terminology structure represents hierarchical formations of concepts defined and connected to each other by relationships, with identifiers for machine use and descriptors for human readability.

Fig. 4: SNOMED CT Design (“SNOMED CT Basics”, n.d.)

SNOMED CT has three types of components:

1. **Concepts:** Represent clinical *meanings* organized into hierarchies, with each concept having one unique numerical identifier for machine use and one or more descriptions for human readers. The January 2020 release of SNOMED CT included as many as 352,567 concepts (“SNOMED CT 5-step briefing”, n.d.).

Concepts vary greatly in type, some of the concept examples include body structures (e.g., entire heart), clinical findings (e.g., bleeding), and organisms (e.g., hepatitis C virus).

2. **Descriptions:** Provide human-understandable terms to the concept. Each concept can have one or more descriptions in each language, and each of these descriptions is, in turn, labelled with a unique description identifier. For example, the description of hepatitis C virus is “62944002 — Hepatitis C virus (organism)”.
3. **Relationships:** Provide links between concepts. There are two types of relationships in SNOMED CT:
 - **Subtype** “*is a*” relationships: relate a concept to its more generic parent concept(s). For example, the concepts |viral hepatitis type B| and |viral hepatitis type C| both have an |is a| relationship to their parent concept |viral hepatitis| which has an |is a| relationship to the concept |hepatitis due to infection| which in turn has |is a| relationships to both the concepts |inflammatory disease of the liver| and |liver disorder due to infection|. The example shows that a concept can have multiple children concepts and multiple parent concepts.
 - **Attribute** relationships: contribute to the definition of the concept in ways other than its placement in the SNOMED CT hierarchy. Attribute relationships vary for different concepts as each has a domain (source concept definition) and a range (destination concept definition). For example, the domain for the attribute |causative agent| can contain any disorder concept (as disorders have causes) but not a body structure concept, and its range can contain organism concepts (like viruses) but not body structures.

As evident from the list of the top-level hierarchies in figure 4, SNOMED CT concepts have the broadest possible definition to enable the representation of any notion. Even the relationships and attributes are considered concepts and are parts of the SNOMED CT hierarchy of concepts; for example, the |is a| relationship falls under the hierarchical path: concept \Rightarrow model component \Rightarrow linkage concept. While it seems counter-intuitive, including relationships under the concepts hierarchy is akin to the common ontological knowledge representation conventions. For example, an ontology represents the fact that Utrecht is a city in the Netherlands using DBpedia resources with the triple form $\langle \text{dbr:Utrecht}, \text{dbo:country}, \text{dbr:Netherlands} \rangle$. The OWL object property `dbo:country` is both a relationship between two resources (a triple predicate) and a resource in and of itself.

2.2.2 SNOMED CT Hierarchies

The top node of the SNOMED CT hierarchy is occupied by the root concept **SNOMED CT concept**, and nineteen direct sub types of it are the **top level**

concepts that provide the structure of the SNOMED CT. These top level concepts are:

1. **Body structure** represents normal and abnormal anatomical structures. For example, the external auditory canal (the external ear canal), which is the location of the infection condition Otitis Externa, is represented by the hierarchical path: *Body structure* \Rightarrow *Anatomical or acquired body structure* \Rightarrow *Anatomical structure* \Rightarrow *Body organ structure* \Rightarrow *Organ part* \Rightarrow *Ear part* \Rightarrow *External ear structure* \Rightarrow *External ear part* \Rightarrow *External auditory canal structure* \Rightarrow *Entire external auditory canal*.
2. **Clinical finding**: represents the result of a clinical observation, assessment or judgment by the physician and includes the concepts to represent diagnoses. For example, the path for the Otitis Externa is: *Clinical finding* \Rightarrow *Finding by site* \Rightarrow *Finding of body region* \Rightarrow *Finding of head and neck region* \Rightarrow *Ear finding* \Rightarrow *Disorder of Ear* \Rightarrow *Disorder of external ear* \Rightarrow *Otitis Externa disorder*.
3. **Situation with explicit context** including risk factors, previous response to treatments, family history, and other contextual factors. For an Otitis Externa case, whether the patient is a swimmer or not is a context for the physician to consider as it is caused by a disturbance in the normal acidic environment of the ear canal, and thus is associated with swimming.
4. **Procedure** includes medical examination procedures, administration of medicines, imaging, education, therapies and administrative procedures.
5. **Observable entity** varies from general observations like age and gender to specific pathological observations (e.g., the appearance of the ear canal for an Otitis Externa patient).
6. **Organism** represents organisms of interests like bacteria and viruses.
7. **Substance** represents the chemical substances whether naturally occurring in the body, associated with a disorder, administered in medications or present in edibles.
8. **Pharmaceutical/biologic product** represents drug products.
9. **Specimen** represents entities or samples obtained from the patient for analysis including blood, fluids, biopsy and others.
10. **Special concept** are ones useful for specific use cases like navigational concepts, accidental cuts, and abnormal findings.
11. **Physical object** like devices and physical implants.
12. **Physical force** represents physical forces that can play a role in injuries like electricity, fire and friction.
13. **Event** represents occurrences excluding procedures and interventions, like traumatic events.
14. **Environments and geographical locations** types of environments like inpatient or outpatient care environments, and locations like countries or locales with different geography.

15. **Social context** like life style and occupation.
16. **Staging and scales** includes a long list of predefined and standard scales to quantify different conditions. Those scales are especially crucial in logging and representing subjective conditions in an objective way, for example, the Glasgow Coma Scale is a clinical scale used to measure a person’s level of consciousness after a brain injury (Teasdale & Jennett, 1974).
17. **Qualifier value** represents the values for some SNOMED CT attributes, including numerical values like dosage.
18. **Record artefact** content representing meta-data about the records created. Including record type, document part, record creator/organizer.
19. **SNOMED CT Model Component** contains technical metadata supporting the SNOMED CT release.

It is clear that not all conditions and medical consultations will use all the available concepts. An Otitis Externa consultation, for example, will include concepts from the top level hierarchies of body structure, observable entity, clinical finding among others; however, it will not include any concepts from specimen, physical force, or physical objects.

2.3 NHG and FMS Medical Guidelines

The Dutch College of General Practitioners (Nederlands Huisartsen Genootschap - NHG) provides guidelines for diagnosing and treating common conditions in general practice (“Nederlands Huisartsen Genootschap NHG - Richtlijnen (Guidelines of The Dutch College of General Practitioners)”, n.d.). The guidelines for various conditions are regularly updated based on new research. They include sections about prognosis, common causes and background, physical examination and diagnosis guidelines, treatment policy, consultations and referral guidelines (if any), and control and future patient check-ups. The symptoms and observations indicating a condition and the treatments recommended for such condition by the NHG guidelines are relevant to the construction and population of the Patient Medical Graph (PMG) and the related ontologies as will be detailed in the coming sections.

Similarly, the Dutch Federation of Medical Specialists (Federatie Medisch Specialisten - FMS) publishes medical guidelines in several specializations (“Federatie Medisch Specialisten FMS - Richtlijnen (Guidelines of The Dutch Federation of Medical Specialists)”, n.d.). The two sets of guidelines overlap for some conditions and should both be considered for a full and comprehensive view of the medical guidelines in the Netherlands; however, only the NHG guidelines are considered for the remainder of this document. Considering both the NHG and FMS guidelines can especially pose a challenge with the collection of data from the guidelines as they use different structures and conventions (figure 5).

Otitis externa

Main changes

Key messages

preface

Wallpapers

Diagnostics guidelines

Policy Guidelines

References

Otitis External

1. Homepage
 2. Differential Diagnosis Acute Otitis Externa
 3. Disease course and treatment Otitis Externa
 4. Optimal Pain Management Acute Otitis Externa
 5. Indicated Treatment Acute Otitis Externa
 6. Topical Treatment Otitis Externa
 7. Duration of treatment Acute Otitis Externa
 8. Administration of medication Acute Otitis Externa
 9. Therapy Resistance Strategy Otitis Externa
 10. Surgery Chronic Otitis External
- Attachments

(a) NHG (“NHG Otitis Externa Guidelines”, n.d.)

(b) FMS (“FMS Otitis Externa Guidelines”, n.d.)

Fig. 5: NHG and FMS guideline hierarchies for the Otitis Externa condition (Google translate: Dutch to English)

While there are advancements in computerized representations of clinical guidelines, they mainly aim at finding ways to support diagnosis and treatment plans (Zamborlini et al., 2016). However, the representation of medical guidelines knowledge to enable the automated summarization of medical consultations is still an open research problem. The literature review did not lead to previous attempts to define a framework to represent such knowledge.

2.4 Automated Medical Consultation Summarization: The Care2Report System

2.4.1 Introducing Care2Report

Arndt et al. (2017) found that primary care physicians spend nearly twice as long on Electronic Health Records systems (EHR) as on direct patient care. Besides the financial cost, administrative burdens take time away from face-to-face interaction with patients and overload the physicians who consequently report rising stress (Babbott et al., 2014) and dissatisfaction with their jobs (Friedberg et al., 2014).

Several efforts tried to use speech recognition technologies to assist the documentation process of medical consultations. However, most of these attempts either focused on the medical practitioner dictation of the consultation report (Ajami,

2016), or the use of audio-only transcription without considering the video and measurements data (Chiu et al., 2017; Klann & Szolovits, 2009). Both approaches are difficult to use in practice as they either interfere with the standard methods of health care practitioners or miss some aspects of the consultation. Therefore, the Care2Report system proposed an approach to reduce the administrative burden by automating the capturing, transcription, analysis, and report generation of medical consultations (Maas et al., 2020). Care2Report follows a rule-based summarization approach rather than a machine-learning one to additionally allow better explainability.

2.4.2 Care2Report Functional Architecture

The system utilizes both third-party and custom-built modules in a loosely-coupled microservices architecture to capture multimodal inputs and process them into a medical consultation report adhering to the Electronic Medical Records (EMR) guidelines (Maas et al., 2020). The summarization pipeline relies on an ontology embodying the vocabulary and guidelines of the field. The information extracted from the conversation is processed and used to populate this ontology to generate the rule-adhering report (Molenaar et al., 2020).

The automated conversation summarization system runs on a kernel of knowledge representation, summarization, and reporting with customizable input and output interfaces that connect it to other systems in the domain. The domain of application governs the system customization and the flow of the summarization processing. This section goes through the different modules of the system and their essential features to give a representation of the workings of the system and its instantiation in different domains.

The **domain customization definition** module prebuilds the ontologies for the application domain before the automated conversation summarization pipeline starts. The module extracts the domain-specific vocabularies, narrative structures, and procedures. It utilizes them to build an ontology encompassing the concepts, properties, and relations to be subsequently populated by the pipeline. This module is the main focus of this research. Maas et al. (2020) provided a model for the formal representation in the field of medical care in the Care2Report system that is the first concrete realization of the automated conversation summarizer. This knowledge graph, called the Patient Medical Graph PMG, will be discussed in details in subsequent sections along with the proposed updates to better fit it to the existing medical ontologies and guidelines. Once the guidelines and standards of a specific illness are formalized into an ontology, they can be populated by specific consultations data (Molenaar et al., 2020).

The conversation is to be recorded in multiple modalities including audio, video, and measurement modes (sensors or measuring devices), and the individual

input devices are connected through the **multimedia recorder** module. The audio input goes through a speaker diarization process to identify and label different speakers, for example, the care provider and the patient in medical applications. The video input is processed for facial blurring to safeguard the privacy of participants, noting also that the facial input is not necessary in subsequent action recognition processes. Finally, the module provides integration to measurement devices and checks for the measured data validity and conformity.

The **summarization processing** module orchestrates the system operations by combining the multimodalities and coordinating between the different microservices of the architecture. It tracks the conversation timeline and the different speakers and satisfies analytics capabilities by providing interfaces to external analytics tools.

In line with the camera input, microphone input, and device measurements of the multimedia recorder module, the **knowledge representation** module provides action recognition, audio transcription, and data analyzer. The conversation knowledge representation engine transforms all the conversation data into semantic triples. The triples are stored, processed and then used to populate the domain ontology to form a conversation knowledge graph to generate the final reports.

The **summarization and reporting** module begins with the algorithmic summarization that selects relevant triples from the narrative based on the domain-specific conventions and abstracts data from the descriptive information. The interactive performance learner deals with corrections, editing and feedback. A natural language generation system fills in the sentence templates defined by the conventions in the knowledge representation module. And finally, the interoperability with other systems, to obtain data or upload reports, is achieved through the **context interface** module.

Figure 6 illustrates the automated conversation summarization functional architecture for a pipeline extending from the multimodal input to the final generation of the natural language report. The functionalities related to pre-building the ontology are the focus of this research, and so the other modules are grayed out.

Fig. 6: Automated Conversation Summarization Functional Architecture

Chapter 3

Patient Medical Graph (PMG)

3.1 Introducing the Patient Medical Graph

Maas et al. (2020) provided a model for the formal representation in the field of medical care in the Care2Report system which is a concrete realization of the automated conversation summarizer. The reference Patient Medical Graph (figure 7), represented the human anatomy (black), signs and symptoms (blue), medical observations (green), diagnosis (red), and treatment plans (orange).

Fig. 7: Reference Graph for the PMG (Maas et al., 2020)

This section presents an updated version of this PMG to incorporate the following main updates:

- **Symptoms** are subjective abnormalities that the patient perceives, while **observations** are objective abnormalities detected by the physician (LeBlond et al., 2015). For example, a patient feeling a fever is a symptom, while the physician detecting an actual increase in body temperature is an observation. Accordingly, the symptoms and observations subgraphs are to be separated. Two motives drive this distinction in the PMG. First, the medical guidelines differentiate between the patient-reported symptoms and the physician’s observations and report them in separate sections. Second, and more importantly, the resulting EMR report includes separate sections for those subjective and objective comments.
- An **anatomical unit** (that can have symptoms, observations, diagnosis, or treatment) can be either an anatomical structure or a function. An **anatomical structure** is “a physical anatomical entity and a physical object, ... it

consists of parts that are themselves anatomical structures”, anatomical structures are “...localized to a specific area or combine and carry out one or more specialized [anatomical] *functions* of an organism.” (Rosse et al., 1998). The function concept is then to be introduced to the PMG to reflect this distinction and to better match the SNOMED CT hierarchies.

Relying on separately (meta)modelling each of the five subgraphs (anatomy, symptoms, observations, diagnosis, and treatment) provides a better understanding of how they build on one another. The resulting Patient Medical Graph provides the notational aspect of the ontology development framework.

Definition 1. *Patient Medical Graph - PMG*

The Patient Medical Graph (PMG) is an all-encompassing knowledge graph representing the patient’s anatomy and symptoms and the physician’s observations, diagnosis and prescribed treatment.

3.2 Recurring Example: Otitis Externa Consultation

As an example to be used for the rest of the document, we use the NHG guideline of the inflammation of external ear canal known as Otitis Externa (“NHG Otitis Externa Guidelines”, n.d.). The condition is chosen as an example for the relative simplicity of the associated guidelines and the lack of complicated medical procedures, terminology, or differential diagnosis.

Research cited in the guidelines suggests that Otitis Externa is caused by a disturbance in the normal acidic environment of the ear canal, and thus is associated with swimming. The symptoms reported by the patient may include ear pain, itching in the ear, fluid drainage from the ear, and hearing loss. The physician may ask about the duration of complaints, previous episodes of ear complaints, recent cold, and past ear surgeries. And in case the condition occurs frequently, the physician may also choose to ask about a possible connection with swimming, irritation from ear picks, using cosmetic products such as soap, shampoo or hair spray, and use of hearing aid among other things. After discussing the symptoms reported by the patient, the physician examines both the complaint-free ear and the affected ear for signs of scars, swelling, flaking, redness, and the state of the eardrum among others.

The guidelines state that the patient is diagnosed with Otitis Externa if exhibiting at least one of the following complaints: ear pain, itching, and otorrhea (ear drainage); in conjunction with at least one of the following findings: redness or swelling of the ear canal, and pain with traction to the auricle. We notice that some symptoms (e.g., hearing loss) are not required for an Otitis Externa diagnosis, indicating that while the PMG and ontological representation of the condition should include it as a possible symptom, some specific consultations might have

this symptom present while others do not. Also, the guidelines indicate that the physician should check the eardrum; however, Otitis Externa is not associated with any observations regarding the eardrum. This may suggest that an observation (e.g., rupture) of the eardrum might indicate a different diagnosis.

As for the treatment, the guidelines recommend that the physician should instruct the patient on how to clean the infected ear properly, and prescribe ear drops. Referral to an ENT specialist or an allergist is recommended in case the condition does not improve in a timely manner or if the patient is from a specific vulnerable group (e.g., elderly and diabetic).

As the PMG (and ultimately the resulting consultation report) aims to represent the conversation between the patient and the physician, rather than support the physician’s decision, the reasoning behind which treatment to choose is beyond our scope. The PMG and its accompanying ontology and knowledge base should contain all treatment possibilities as options, while the physician’s discretion will decide which ones to use.

As an example, we consider a fictitious consultation for a patient suffering from an external ear canal inflammation (Otitis Externa). The conversation and physician examination indicate the following:

- The patient did not suffer from the condition before, and was afflicted by the symptom for a short period (acute rather than chronic, thus matching the chosen guidelines).
- The only symptom described by the patient is ear pain. No indication of itching, fluid drainage, or hearing loss.
- Upon examination, the physician observed swelling, redness, and skin flaking in the external ear canal.

3.3 Analyzing the Patient Medical Graph

The medical report produced by the automated conversation summarization system Care2Report to upload into the Electronic Medical Records (EMR) follows a predefined structure of four sections: subjective (what the patient reports), objective (what the physician identifies), evaluation (assessment and diagnosis), and plan for treatment and follow up (Cameron & Turtle-Song, 2002). Following the same reasoning, the Patient Medical Graph PMG consists of a composite of four subgraphs reflecting the four aspects of reporting and a fifth foundational subgraph for human anatomy.

The following subsections introduce all five subgraphs, each building upon the previous one(s). For each subgraph, an abstract meta-model figure defines the concepts considered by the model, a reference PMG-format representation of the subgraph is presented, and finally, an instantiation of the subgraph in the

context of Otitis Externa and the specific patient consultation described above are presented (if applicable).

The PMG and its instantiation with information from specific consultation provide a graphical representation of ontology-based knowledge where every two concepts and the relationship between them form a triple. Examples of such triples are introduced in the coming subsection when relevant.

3.3.1 Patient Anatomy Graph

The Patient Anatomy Graph is the foundation for the knowledge representation in the PMG. The PAG can be built based on existing resources like the Foundational Model of Anatomy (Rosse & Mejino Jr, 2003), or it can utilize an existing hierarchical terminology structure like SNOMED CT, which will be the case in this research. Within the SNOMED CT hierarchies, the human anatomy is represented in the path: *SNOMED CT concept* \Rightarrow *Body structure* \Rightarrow *Anatomical or acquired body structure*.

Figure 8a lays the foundation for the model used in the PAG where an anatomical unit (that can have symptoms, observations, diagnosis, or treatment) can be either an anatomical structure or a function, as previously established. Also, note that a complete definition of an anatomical unit includes the patient concept.

Definition 2. Patient Anatomy Graph - PAG

The Patient Anatomy Graph is a knowledge graph depicting all the human anatomical structures and functions.

Definition 3. Anatomical Structure

An anatomical structure is a physical anatomical entity or a physical object that can consist of parts that are themselves anatomical structures.

Definition 4. Anatomical Function

An anatomical function is a task performed by an anatomical structure or a group of anatomical structures.

Definition 5. Anatomical Unit

An anatomical unit is a component of the human anatomy as represented in the patient anatomy graph that can have symptoms, observations, diagnosis, or treatment. Anatomical units, in this definition, encompass both anatomical structures and functions.

Figure 8b shows the reference PMG notation representation of the patient anatomy, while figure 8c represents the anatomy related to Otitis Externa. The anatomy of the ear (anatomical structure) consists of several parts including the external auditory canal and the eardrum (both are also anatomical structure), and the ear is associated with hearing (anatomical function).

In subsequent (sub)graphs, an additional figure will represent the specific consultation’s instantiation from the introduction section. However, as the anatomy of the human ear is (mostly) identical, figure 8c represents both the general anatomy of the ear, and that of the specific patient.

The PAG can be represented in triples, for example, the partial ear PAG related to Otitis Externa is as follows:

- <externalAuditoryCanal, isPartOf, ear>
- <eardrum, isPartOf, ear>
- <ear, isPartOf, head>
- <head, isPartOf, patient>
- <ear, hasFunction, hearing>

3.3.2 Patient Symptoms Graph

Both symptoms and observations reveal essential information about the patient’s condition; however, there is a lack of agreement on the distinction between the two concepts (Cox et al., 2014). For the development of the PMG, we will adopt the definitions that correspond best to the distinction between the subjective and objective sections of the EMR report: **symptoms** are subjective abnormalities that the patient perceives, while **observations** are objective abnormalities detected by the physician (LeBlond et al., 2015). For example, a patient feeling a fever is a symptom, while the physician detecting an actual increase in body temperature is an observation.

It is worth noting that some abnormalities can be both symptoms and observations based on the context, which is one of the challenges of developing the system and the underlying ontology. For example, a patient noticing a redness of the knee while walking is a symptom (perceived by the patient and reported in the subjective section of the EMR report), while a redness in the ear canal examined by the physician and not noticeable by the patient is an observation (detected by the physician and reported in the objective section of the EMR report). Thus, the concept “redness” can be both a symptom or an observation in the ontology.

Previous Care2Report research did not differentiate between the complaints reported by the patient (referred to here as symptoms) and the abnormalities detected by the physician (referred to here as observations); they were together called *symptoms and signs*, while their existence and degree were denoted by an *observation*. However, since the formalization of the distinction between symptoms and observations is an essential aspect of the PMG and the related ontology definition, the term “*sign*” is dropped as it does not equate to either category.

Definition 6. *Symptom*

A symptom is a subjective abnormality that the patient perceives (LeBlond et al., 2015).

(a) Meta-model of the Patient Anatomy Graph

(b) Patient Anatomy Graph reference notations

(c) Example PAG of the Otitis Externa condition

Fig. 8: The Patient Anatomy Graph (PAG)

Definition 7. *Patient Symptoms Graph - PSG*

The Patient Symptoms Graph is a knowledge graph representing all the complaints and anomalies (symptoms) reported by the patient.

Figure 9 expands on the previously discussed PAG, and introduces a new representation for the specific patient consultation (figure 9d). The dimmed (low opacity) parts of the figure reflect that the patient does not suffer from those specific symptoms.

The figures show that Otitis Externa is associated with four possible symptoms: drainage, itching, pain, and hearing loss. Of those, the first three are related to an anatomical structure (external auditory canal) and the last is related to a function (hearing).

For the specific consultation in question, the patient only suffers from pain, a symptom associated with the anatomical structure of the external ear canal. The patient therefore does not suffer from any function-related symptom.

(a) Meta-model of the Patient Symptoms Graph

(b) Patient Symptoms Graph reference notations

(c) Example PSG of the Otitis Externa condition

(d) Example PSG of an Otitis Externa patient

Fig. 9: The Patient Symptoms Graph
(PAG + PSG)

The pain symptom can be represented by the following triples:

- <externalAuditoryCanal, hasSymptom, symp_2 >
- <symp_2, symptom, earPain>
- <symp_2, hasValue, 7/10 >

3.3.3 Patient Observations Graph

The Patient Observations Graph depicts the physician’s observations as opposed to the PSG that deals with the patient-reported symptoms, as indicated in the previous section.

Definition 8. *Observation*

An observation is an objective abnormality detected by the physician (LeBlond et al., 2015).

Definition 9. *Patient Observations Graph - POG*

The patient Observation Graph is a knowledge graph representing all the observations made by the physician about the patient’s condition.

Figure 10 expands on the PAG by including the physician’s observations. Similarly, the dimmed (low opacity) parts reflect that the patient does not exhibit those observations. The possible observations for Otitis Externa Externa according to NHG guidelines include scars, swelling, flaking, and redness; all of them are related to the anatomical structure not the function of hearing. The patient in question exhibits swelling, skin flaking, and redness.

As an example , the redness observation can be represented by the following triples:

- <externalAuditoryCanal, hasObservation, obs_1 >
- <obs_1, observation, redness>
- <obs_2, hasValue, yes >

(a) Meta-model of the Patient Observations Graph

(b) Patient Observations Graph reference notations

(c) Example POG of the Otitis Externa condition

(d) Example POG of an Otitis Externa patient

Fig. 10: The Patient Observations Graph
(PAG + POG)

3.3.4 Patient Diagnosis Graph

The Patient Diagnosis Graph represents the diagnosis uncovered by the physician.

Definition 10. *Diagnosis*

A diagnosis is a condition or disease identification by the physician based on the symptoms and observations.

Definition 11. *Patient Diagnosis Graph - PDG*

The Patient Diagnosis Graph is a knowledge graph describing the physician’s diagnosis of the patient’s condition.

Figure 11 puts together the symptoms and observations and expand on them by introducing the diagnosis, Otitis Externa in this case. The automated conversation summarization system does not aim at decision support, and thus, the diagnosis needs to be specified by the physician.

For abbreviation, the different symptoms and observations are textually separated by a / character. The main triple observed in the graph states that the patient is diagnosed with Otitis Externa: <patient, diagnosedWith, OtitisExterna>.

(a) Meta-model of the Patient Diagnosis Graph

(b) Patient Diagnosis Graph reference notations

(c) Example PDG of the Otitis Externa condition

(d) Example PDG of an Otitis Externa patient

Fig. 11: The Patient Diagnosis Graph
(PAG + PSG + POG + POG)

3.3.5 Patient Treatment Graph

Treatment in this context is defined broadly as medications, instructions for the patient to follow (e.g., cleaning), referral to a specialist, or any other procedure.

Definition 12. *Treatment*

A treatment encompasses any physician's prescription, including medications, instructions for the patient to follow, referral to a specialist, further tests, or any other procedure.

Definition 13. *Patient Treatment Graph - PTG*

The Patient Treatment Graph is a knowledge graph describing all the treatments prescribed by the physician, including medications, instructions, referrals, or additional medical tests.

Figure 12 introduces the last constituent of the PMG: the treatment. The two treatments depicted in the graph are ear cleaning and ear drops, and they can be represented with the following triples:

- <patient, treatedWith, cleaning>
- <patient, treatedWith, earDrops>

The addition of more treatments or more details about the treatment (e.g., which ear drops) add more triples and more edges to the graph.

(a) Meta-model of the Patient Treatment Graph

(b) Patient Treatment Graph reference notations

(c) Example PTG of the Otitis Externa condition

(d) Example PTG of an Otitis Externa patient

Fig. 12: The Patient Treatment Graph
 $(PMG = PAG + PSG + POG + PDG + PTG)$

3.4 Formal Representations of the PMG

The structure and the interaction between the various subgraphs are relatively intuitive for simple conditions concerning comparatively simple body structures. However, adding the complete human anatomy and the guidelines from several medical authorities can make the graphs less intuitive to understand and communicate. Therefore, it is essential to introduce formal descriptions of the subgraphs and their components; this section introduces a few of these descriptions.

As discussed before, the PMG is an all-encompassing knowledge graph representing the patient’s anatomy and symptoms and the physician’s observations, diagnosis and prescribed treatment:

$$\text{PMG} = \text{PAG} \cup \text{PSG} \cup \text{POG} \cup \text{PDG} \cup \text{PTG}$$

Formally defining the PMG and its subgraphs requires the definition of the following sets:

Set	Description
B	all anatomical structures of the body
F	all anatomical functions of the body
A	all anatomical units ($A = B \cup F$)
P	all patients (A patient is also an anatomical unit: $P \subset A$)
S	all medical symptoms (reported by the patient).
O	all medical observations (observed by the physician).
V	all possible values to be assigned to symptoms $s \in S$ or observations $o \in O$.
D	all medical diagnoses.
E	all explicit diagnoses.
I	all implicit diagnoses.
T	all medical treatments.

Table 2: Sets Required to Define the PMG

The formal definitions of the subgraphs comprising the PMG are the following:

Graph	Vertices	Edges
PAG	$A = B \cup F$	$\{(b_1, b_2) \mid b_1, b_2 \in B \wedge b_1 \text{ is a direct anatomical sub-part of } b_2$ \vee $(b, f) \mid b \in B \wedge f \in F \wedge b \text{ has an anatomical function } f\}$.
PSG	$A \cup S \cup V$	$\{(a, s), (s, v) \mid a \in A \wedge s \in S \wedge v \in V\}$ i.e., all symptoms.
POG	$A \cup O \cup V$	$\{(a, o), (o, v) \mid a \in A \wedge o \in O \wedge v \in V\}$ i.e., all observations.
PDG	$P \cup D$	$\{(p, d) \mid p \in P \wedge d \in D\}$ i.e., all the diagnoses of patient p .
PTG	$P \cup T$	$\{(p, t) \mid p \in P \wedge t \in T\}$ i.e., all the treatments of patient p .

Table 3: Formal Definitions of the Subgraphs Comprising the PMG

Finally, some of the rules that need to be coded into the system to define the relationships between the entities in the different subgraphs are listed below, consulting domain experts is expected to add to this list:

1. Each anatomical structure (b) is a part of another anatomical structure (b) unless it is the complete body structure (b*).
 $\forall b_1 \exists b_2 : \text{isPartOf}(b_1, b_2) \qquad b_1, b_2 \in B, \neg (b_1 = b^*)$
2. Each function (f) is assigned to one or more anatomical structure (b).
 $\forall f \exists b : \text{hasFunction}(b, f) \qquad b \in B, f \in F$
3. Each symptom (s) is associated with one or more anatomical unit (a).
 $\forall s \exists a : \text{hasSymptom}(a, s) \qquad s \in S, a \in A$
4. Each observation (o) is associated with one or more anatomical unit (a).
 $\forall o \exists a : \text{hasObservation}(a, o) \qquad o \in O, a \in A$
5. A patient (p) is diagnosed with a diagnosis (d).
 $\forall p \exists d : \text{diagnosedWith}(p, d) \qquad p \in P, d \in D$
6. A patient (p) is treated with a treatment (t).
 $\forall p \exists t : \text{treatedWith}(p, t) \qquad p \in P, t \in T$
7. An explicit diagnosis (e) is associated with a symptom (s) or an observation (o).
 $\forall e \exists s \exists o : \text{associatedWith}(s, e) \vee \text{associatedWith}(o, e)$
 $e \in E, s \in S, o \in O$
8. An implicit diagnosis is not explicit. That is, an implicit diagnosis (i) is neither associated with a symptom (s) nor an observation (o).
 $\forall i \forall e : \neg (i = e) \qquad i \in I, e \in E$

Chapter 4

Method for Medical Ontologies Learning

The previous chapter introduced the Patient Medical Graph (PMG) formalisation and the corresponding ontology from a notational perspective. This chapter introduces the procedural perspective of using the anatomical hierarchies of the SNOMED CT along with the medical guidelines to produce ontologies for different diseases and medical conditions. This chapter builds on the notational model provided in the previous one by outlining the procedural method of ontology learning. That is, the PMG models the knowledge while the PDD explains how actually to construct it.

4.1 Process-Deliverable Diagram for Ontology Learning

The Process-Deliverable Diagram model (PDD) introduced by van de Weerd and Brinkkemper (2009), illustrates the activities and artefacts of a specific process. The model depicts the activities on the left-hand side of the PDD diagram using UML activity diagram notations (Omg, 2003), while the deliverables are on the right-hand side of the diagram using UML class diagram notations (Omg, 2003). The model emphasizes the relationships between the activities and their deliverables by connecting them with dotted arrows across the diagram (van de Weerd & Brinkkemper, 2009).

For all the distinctions between the processes to develop various parts of the ontology corresponding to the subgraphs of the PMG, they all follow the same general high-level pattern to build the relevant ontology based on the list of extracted potential concepts from the guidelines (figure 13). Potential concepts are mapped at each stage to both the relevant sections of the guidelines (e.g., physical examination and treatment policy) and the relevant hierarchies of the SNOMED CT (e.g., findings and disorders). The concepts that show in both relevant modules are the appropriate concepts for the ontology at hand (e.g., anatomical structure concept, symptom concept, observation concept or treatment concept).

Fig. 13: General Pattern for Ontology Learning from Guidelines

Figure(14) depicts the used PDD, in which the process is broken down into the following main activities. For simplicity, activities 3-7 are illustrated (and manually performed) sequentially; however, they can also be executed in parallel.

Fig. 14: PDD of the Ontology Learning Method

1. **Target guideline preparation:**The target guideline of the medical condition is selected from the medical authority’s website and is then translated (if necessary) scraped and prepared for the following concept extraction activity. The preparation might include setting the text in a specific structure or format used by the text extraction tool (when applicable).
2. **Concept extraction:** The relevant sections of the guidelines are identified, including sections describing symptoms, physical examination, and treatment plans. As nouns are the natural language representation of things, ideas and notions, they identify the concepts to be extracted (rather than other parts of speech). Thus, the potential concepts to extract are all nouns and noun phrases in the relevant sections that will later be mapped against the SNOMED CT to identify the constituent concepts of the ontology (e.g., anatomical units, symptoms, observations, and treatments). Some potential concepts will not be used in the ontology as they represent general nouns used in the text.

While this activity is manually performed in this research, future research should decide on the tools to automatically extract the concepts and whether there is a distinction between the nouns and noun phrases extracted.

3. **Patient Anatomy Graph (PAG) construction:** The pattern shown in figure (13) applies from this activity, in which the guideline concepts corresponding to SNOME CT *anatomical concepts* are identified and converted into a hierarchy from which the PAG ontology is constructed.
4. **Patient Symptoms Graph (PSG) construction:** The concepts identified in the medical guideline sections describing symptoms are mapped against the corresponding SNOMED CT hierarchies (*findings* and *disorders*) to build the PSG ontology.
5. **Patient Observations Graph (POG) construction:** Similar to the previous activity except dealing with physician observations instead of patient-described symptoms. Thus, the relevant guideline sections are different.
6. **Patient Diagnosis Graph (PDG) construction:** The medical condition or disease discussed in the guideline is the diagnosis associated with symptoms and observations to construct the PDG ontology. The diagnosis is mentioned in several sections of the medical guidelines, and thus it is not necessary to identify relevant sections as in the previous activities.
7. **Patient Treatment Graph (PTG) construction:** The concepts identified in the treatment-related sections of the guideline are mapped against the corresponding SNOMED CT hierarchies (*procedure*, *substance*, *dose form*, and *physical object*) to build the PTG ontology.
8. **Patient Medical Graph Finalization:** All the previous subgraphs and the resultant sub ontologies are combined along with needed information (e.g., prefixes) to construct the complete PMG. This activity also includes checks to validity by confirming the lack of disjoint concepts.

Figure 15 introduces a more detailed depiction of the PDD, including sub-activities and concepts and the relationships between them. Appendix(1) introduces the activities table, providing a complete description of the (sub)activities, and the concepts table providing a description of the associated deliverables.

Fig. 15: Detailed PDD of the Ontology Learning Method

4.2 Applying the PDD to Otitis Externa Guideline

Applying the procedure outlined in the PDD of figure (15) to the Otitis Externa condition (the running example from the previous chapter) produces the ontology in appendix (2). Additionally, the WebVOWL web application (Lohmann et al., 2016) is used to provide an interactive visualization of the ontology. The outcome is illustrated in figure (16).²

For conciseness, the ontology in appendix (2) and the corresponding visualization do not contain the top-level classes (anatomy, symptom, observation, diagnosis, and treatment) and the *subClassOf* relationship linking the other concepts to them. An example of those class definitions and relation triples would be:

c2r:symptom, rdf:type, owl:Class.

c2r:hearingLoss, rdfs:subClassOf, c2r:symptom.

Finally, appendix (3) provides another example of the ontology generation and the resulting WebVOWL visualization of another condition named Acute Rhinosinusitis, a short term inflammation of the sinuses.

² A clearer SVG version of the figure can be accessed here.

Fig. 16: WebVOWL Visualization of the Otitis Externa

4.3 Inclusion of Synonyms

Each of the 352,567 concepts of SNOMED CT (January 2020 release) has one or more descriptors (names) for human readability. One of the descriptors is the fully specified name of the concept (e.g., Otitis Externa) and the rest are synonyms (e.g., swimmer’s ear, inflammation of ear canal). In the example ontologies of this research, we included synonyms only if the term used as the fully specified name (the official name) in SNOMED CT differs from the name in the medical guidelines in use. For example, the anatomical structure officially known in SNOMED CT as tympanic membrane structure is mentioned in the guidelines with a synonym: eardrum. The relationship between the two synonyms is represented by the OWL predicate *owl:sameAs*.

This research did not include all the synonyms to all the concepts used for the sake of brevity and legible visual representation in the WebVOWL figures representing the ontologies (figures 16 and 17). However, a complete ontology for medical consultations summarization should include all synonyms of all concepts mentioned as different medical practitioners may use different synonyms to refer to the same thing. It is a straightforward process to include such synonyms as the OWL ontology obtained from the SNOMED CT hierarchy already contains the *owl:sameAs* triples to identify synonyms.

4.4 The Care2Report Ontology Research Versions

The Care2Report team previously used the Protégé application (Musen, 2015) with modified plugins (e.g., NaturalOWL2) to generate a backbone ontology that was manually edited and expanded. The team based that ontology on the same Otitis Externa guidelines used in this research, alongside data from actual medical consultations³. The resultant extensive ontology (previous ontology) differs from the one produced in this research (new ontology) in several aspects.

On a fundamental level, the two ontology-building attempts approached the process from different perspectives resulting in different outcomes. The new ontology is based on the PMG to define the five subgraphs independently, thus allowing new medical conditions to be added to the existing ontology. A new guideline can expand the ontology by appending the new diagnosis and connecting it to the existing definitions of anatomy, symptoms, observations, and treatments; and adding more if the existing concepts are insufficient to represent the guideline fully. For example, another medical condition that affects the external ear canal can be integrated into the already existing ontology of the Otitis Externa utilizing the existing anatomical hierarchies and some of the defined symptoms, observations, and even treatments. The difference between the two conditions would be easily

³ An SVG file containing a WebVOWL visualisation of the previous ontology can be accessed here.

discernible because they do not identically relate to the same symptoms, observations and treatments. The addition of each new guideline will serve to enrich the ontology with new concepts that, in turn, facilitate the quicker addition of more guidelines.

On the other hand, the previous ontology was organised around four top-level classes (anatomy, symptom, observation, and treatment), while the diagnosis was not explicit. That means that the ontology was developed to represent one condition (Otitis Externa), and adding other conditions (even when similar) would require significantly more effort. The difference in approaches can be attributed to the different starting points: the previous ontology started from the challenging mission of (semi-)automatically building an ontology from a specific medical guideline. In contrast, the new ontology started from the more systematic problem of defining a framework for learning ontologies from medical guidelines.

On a more practical level, the previous ontology was quicker to generate and validate as it used an automated approach in some of the steps rather than relying solely on manual processes. Nevertheless, the automation process added concepts and classes from the guidelines to the ontology that would not be reported in the medical consultation report automatically (by the Care2Report system) and that the physician and the patient would not explicitly mention (e.g., measurements, instruments, and dosages). The new ontology did not include such concepts. The Otitis Externa guideline yielded 73 classes in the previous ontology-building process instead of 33 classes in the new ontology.

	Previous C2R Ontology Research	New Ontology Research
Aim	Specific ontology (semi-)automatically	Framework for learning ontologies from guidelines
Main classes	Anatomy, symptom, observation, treatment	Diagnosis, anatomy, symptom, observation, treatment
Speed	Quick (semi-automatic)	Slow (manual)
Otitis Externa	73 classes	33 classes

Table 4: The Care2Report Ontologies

Chapter 5

Limitations and Future Research

The research detailed in this thesis aimed to create a framework for the systematic learning of medical ontologies from the SNOMED CT terminology and anatomical hierarchies, combined with the medical guidelines of different medical conditions. The coming sections list some of the framework’s limitations, the envisioned future work for the ontology development, and how it fits into the future of the Care2Report system.

5.1 Research Limitations

The research applied the developed framework to generate ontologies for only two conditions: Otitis Externa (in details) and Acute Rhinosinusitis (fewer details). Further, both implementations were based on guidelines from the same medical authority, the Dutch College of General Practitioners (NHG). The guidelines used are for relatively simple conditions with a precise overarching diagnosis for the symptoms and observations detailed in the guidelines and a list of treatments. Not all guidelines are of equal simplicity to apply the framework, as some guidelines deal with more complex and varying conditions. For example, the NHG guideline for “Non-traumatic knee complaints” details a method for differentiating between various similar conditions and thus does not follow the same divided sections typical in most of the NHG guidelines.

Moreover, some guidelines only point the physician towards the tests and indicators to check without actually detailing the results or values to look for, presumably because the results are hard to detail in the text while the medical professionals understand them. For example, the guidelines advise performing an EKG test in several cardiovascular conditions without detailing the expected outcomes. This lack of detailed outcome is particularly challenging for the automated summarization of medical consultations as the findings of such tests would not usually be explicitly communicated to the patient (for being too technical), while the physician might still need to include them in the report. The Care2Report multi-modal input architecture (Maas et al., 2020) aims to eventually allow the integration of (some of) the measurement data, but an ontology to represent this knowledge still needs to be developed.

Finally, as discussed earlier, the SNOMED CT system does not directly link a function to the anatomical structure that performs it; this link is currently identified manually. While it is relatively simple to identify these links in the

examples discussed in this research (e.g., hearing is a function of the ear), domain experts are needed to identify the link between functions and anatomical structures in more complex and less obvious situations.

The Incompatibility of Geriatric Medicine Consultations

As different members of the Care2Report team research various areas of the medical field and different stages of the system's implementation, it became apparent that the domain might be too diverse to fit into one set of frameworks for knowledge representation and reporting. Currently, the most obvious case of this challenging variation is geriatric medicine.

The typical geriatric medicine consultation lasts longer than a standard medical consultation. It aims at assessing the patient's ability to perform tasks and functions independently (e.g., using the stairs, eating, dressing and undressing). Therefore, these consultations can not be processed into symptoms and observations to fit an ontology produced by the framework discussed in this research.

5.2 Future Research

Expanding the Framework

The framework as it stands does not formalize the process of associating anatomical functions (e.g., hearing) to the relevant anatomical structure (e.g., ear). As SNOMED CT does not provide such a link, more research is needed to determine another way to perform this task, either through experts' opinions or other data sources.

Additionally, as discussed in the previous section, non-typical consultations, including geriatric medicine consultations, do not provide knowledge that fit the framework. More research is needed to define a way to construct ontologies for such cases.

Finally, the measurement inputs obtained by the multi-modal capabilities of the Care2Report system should be systematically represented in the ontology to supplement the summarized conversation in generating the medical report.

Validating the Framework

More guidelines should validate the framework both from the NHG and from other international medical authorities. The inclusion of more guidelines to supplement the existing ontologies should prove beneficial, especially when one guideline does not provide enough details (e.g., the previously mentioned case of using EKG in cardiovascular diseases). Evaluating the generated ontologies in context, the next step of the engineering cycle as described by Wieringa (2014) relies on the further development of the Care2Report system to operate in real consultations.

Automating the Method

The framework was applied manually for the two medical conditions discussed, which required substantial time investment. While validating the framework and completing the prototype phases of the Care2Report system can use manually produced ontologies, the full implementation potential of the system relies on developing an automatic process to generate ontologies of all medical conditions using guidelines from various countries and in different languages.

The ontology relies on data from two sources: SNOMED CT and the medical guidelines. SNOMED CT is a hierarchical clinical terminology that can be directly transformed into an OWL ontology with relatively few steps, and thus it does not pose a challenge to automation effort.

On the other hand, the medical guidelines are text-based descriptions that pose the real challenge for knowledge extraction and structuring. Other Care2Report team members are trying to automate the process of converting the guideline text into ontologies, but there are still complex challenges.

References

- Ajami, S. (2016). Use of speech-to-text technology for documentation by health-care providers. *The National medical journal of India*, 29(3), 148.
- Antoniou, G., & Van Harmelen, F. (2004). *A semantic web primer*. MIT press.
- Arndt, B. G., Beasley, J. W., Watkinson, M. D., Temte, J. L., Tuan, W.-J., Sinsky, C. A., & Gilchrist, V. J. (2017). Tethered to the ehr: Primary care physician workload assessment using ehr event log data and time-motion observations. *The Annals of Family Medicine*, 15(5), 419–426.
- Babbott, S., Manwell, L. B., Brown, R., Montague, E., Williams, E., Schwartz, M., Hess, E., & Linzer, M. (2014). Electronic medical records and physician stress in primary care: Results from the memo study. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 21(e1), e100–e106.
- Berners-Lee, T., Hendler, J., & Lassila, O. (2001). The semantic web. *Scientific american*, 284(5), 34–43.
- Bodenreider, O., Cornet, R., & Vreeman, D. J. (2018). Recent developments in clinical terminologies—snomed ct, loinc, and rxnorm. *Yearbook of medical informatics*, 27(1), 129.
- Callahan, A., Cruz-Toledo, J., Ansell, P., & Dumontier, M. (2013). Bio2rdf release 2: Improved coverage, interoperability and provenance of life science linked data. *Extended Semantic Web Conference*, 200–212.
- Cameron, S., & Turtle-Song, I. (2002). Learning to write case notes using the soap format. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 80(3), 286–292.
- Care2report-mission. (n.d.). <https://sites.google.com/view/care2report/mission?authuser=0>
- Chiu, C.-C., Tripathi, A., Chou, K., Co, C., Jaitly, N., Jaunzeikare, D., Kannan, A., Nguyen, P., Sak, H., Sankar, A., et al. (2017). Speech recognition for medical conversations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.07274*.
- Cox, A. P., Ray, P. L., Jensen, M., & Diehl, A. D. (2014). Defining ‘sign’ and ‘symptom’. *TABLE&OF&CONTENTS*, 42.
- Dalgliesh, J. (2016). How the enterprise knowledge graph connects oil and gas data silos. <https://www.maana.io/blog/enterprise-knowledge-graph-connects-oil-gas-data-silos/>
- Decker, S., Mitra, P., & Melnik, S. (2000). Framework for the semantic web: An rdf tutorial. *IEEE Internet Computing*, 4(6), 68–73.
- El-Sappagh, S., Franda, F., Ali, F., & Kwak, K.-S. (2018). Snomed ct standard ontology based on the ontology for general medical science. *BMC medical informatics and decision making*, 18(1), 1–19.

- Federatie medisch specialisten fms - richtlijnen (guidelines of the dutch federation of medical specialists)*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 25, 2021, from <https://richtlijndatabase.nl/>
- Ferras, H., Liu, I., & Xing Zhang, X. (2018). Food discovery with uber eats: Building a query understanding engine. <https://eng.uber.com/uber-eats-query-understanding/>
- Fms otitis externa guidelines*. (n.d.). Retrieved May 18, 2021, from https://richtlijndatabase.nl/richtlijn/otitis_externa/otitis_externa_-_korte_beschrijving.html
- Friedberg, M. W., Chen, P. G., Van Busum, K. R., Aunon, F., Pham, C., Caloyeras, J., Mattke, S., Pitchforth, E., Quigley, D. D., Brook, R. H., et al. (2014). Factors affecting physician professional satisfaction and their implications for patient care, health systems, and health policy. *Rand health quarterly*, 3(4).
- Genesereth, M., & Nilsson, N. (1987). Logical foundations of artificial intelligence.
- Gruber, T. R. (1993). A translation approach to portable ontology specifications. *Knowledge acquisition*, 5(2), 199–220.
- Harris, S., Seaborne, A., & Prud'hommeaux, E. (2013). Sparql 1.1 query language. *W3C recommendation*, 21(10), 778.
- He, Q. (2016). Building the linkedin knowledge graph. <https://engineering.linkedin.com/blog/2016/10/building-the-linkedin-knowledge-graph/>
- Hendler, J., Holm, J., Musialek, C., & Thomas, G. (2012). Us government linked open data: Semantic. data. gov. *IEEE Annals of the History of Computing*, 27(03), 25–31.
- Higham, N. J. (2005). *King arthur: Myth-making and history*. Routledge.
- Hitzler, P., Krotzsch, M., & Rudolph, S. (2009). *Foundations of semantic web technologies*. CRC press.
- Hogan, A., Blomqvist, E., Cochez, M., d'Amato, C., de Melo, G., Gutierrez, C., Gayo, J. E. L., Kirrane, S., Neumaier, S., Polleres, A., et al. (2020). Knowledge graphs. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.02320*.
- Klann, J. G., & Szolovits, P. (2009). An intelligent listening framework for capturing encounter notes from a doctor-patient dialog. *BMC medical informatics and decision making*, 9(S1), S3.
- Köhler, S., Vasilevsky, N. A., Engelstad, M., Foster, E., McMurry, J., Aymé, S., Baynam, G., Bello, S. M., Boerkoel, C. F., Boycott, K. M., et al. (2017). The human phenotype ontology in 2017. *Nucleic acids research*, 45(D1), D865–D876.
- Krishnan, A. (2018). Making search easier. <https://www.aboutamazon.com/news/innovation-at-amazon/making-search-easier/>

- LeBlond, R. F. et al. (2015). *Degowin's diagnostic examination*. McGraw-Hill Education New York, NY.
- Lehmann, J., Isele, R., Jakob, M., Jentzsch, A., Kontokostas, D., Mendes, P. N., Hellmann, S., Morsey, M., Van Kleef, P., Auer, S., et al. (2015). Dbpedia—a large-scale, multilingual knowledge base extracted from wikipedia. *Semantic web*, 6(2), 167–195.
- Lohmann, S., Negru, S., Haag, F., & Ertl, T. (2016). Visualizing ontologies with vowl. *Semantic Web*, 7(4), 399–419.
- Maas, L., Geurtsen, M., Nouwt, F., Schouten, S., Van De Water, R., Van Dulmen, S., Dalpiaz, F., Van Deemter, K., & Brinkkemper, S. (2020). The care2report system: Automated medical reporting as an integrated solution to reduce administrative burden in healthcare. *Proceedings of the 53rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*.
- McGuinness, D. L., & Van Harmelen, F. (2004). Owl web ontology language overview. *W3C recommendation*, 10(10), 2004.
- Miller, E. (1998). An introduction to the resource description framework. *Bulletin of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 25(1), 15–19.
- Molenaar, S., Maas, L., Burriel, V., Dalpiaz, F., & Brinkkemper, S. (2020). Medical dialogue summarization for automated reporting in healthcare. *International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering*, 76–88.
- Musen, M. A. (2015). The protégé project: A look back and a look forward. *AI matters*, 1(4), 4–12.
- Nederlands huisartsen genootschap nhg - richtlijnen (guidelines of the dutch college of general practitioners)*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 25, 2021, from <https://richtlijnen.nhg.org/>
- Nhg otitis externa guidelines*. (n.d.). Retrieved May 18, 2021, from <https://richtlijnen.nhg.org/standaarden/otitis-externa#volledige-tekst>
- Nhg otitis externa guidelines*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 25, 2021, from <https://richtlijnen.nhg.org/standaarden/otitis-externa>
- Omg, M. (2003). Model driven architecture guide version 1.0.1. *Object Management Group*, 62, 34.
- Petasis, G., Karkaletsis, V., Paliouras, G., Krithara, A., & Zavitsanos, E. (2011). Ontology population and enrichment: State of the art. *Knowledge-driven multimedia information extraction and ontology evolution*, 134–166.
- Rosse, C., Mejino, J., Modayur, B., Jakobovits, R., Hinshaw, K., & Brinkley, J. (1998). Motivation and organizational principles for the digital anatomist symbolic knowledge base: An approach toward standards in anatomical knowledge representation. *J Am Med Inform Assoc*, 5, 17–40.

- Rosse, C., & Mejino Jr, J. L. (2003). A reference ontology for biomedical informatics: The foundational model of anatomy. *Journal of biomedical informatics*, 36(6), 478–500.
- Rudin, C. (2019). Stop explaining black box machine learning models for high stakes decisions and use interpretable models instead. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 1(5), 206–215.
- Shrivastava, S. (2017). Bring rich knowledge of people, places, things and local businesses to your apps. <https://blogs.bing.com/search-quality-insights/2017-07/bring-rich-knowledge-of-people-places-things-and-local-businesses-to-your-apps/>
- Singhal, A. (2012). Introducing the knowledge graph: Things, not strings. <https://blog.google/products/search/introducing-knowledge-graph-things-not/>
- Snomed ct 5-step briefing*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 25, 2021, from <https://www.snomed.org/snomed-ct/five-step-briefing>
- Snomed ct basics*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 25, 2021, from <https://confluence.ihtsdotools.org/display/DOCSTART/4.+SNOMED+CT+Basics>
- Stadler, C., Lehmann, J., Höffner, K., & Auer, S. (2012). Linkedgeodata: A core for a web of spatial open data. *Semantic Web*, 3(4), 333–354.
- Teasdale, G., & Jennett, B. (1974). Assessment of coma and impaired consciousness: A practical scale. *The Lancet*, 304(7872), 81–84.
- van de Weerd, I., & Brinkkemper, S. (2009). Meta-modeling for situational analysis and design methods. *Handbook of research on modern systems analysis and design technologies and applications* (pp. 35–54). IGI Global.
- Vrandečić, D., & Krötzsch, M. (2014). Wikidata: A free collaborative knowledgebase. *Communications of the ACM*, 57(10), 78–85.
- Wieringa, R. J. (2014). *Design science methodology for information systems and software engineering*. Springer.
- Wong, W., Liu, W., & Bennamoun, M. (2012). Ontology learning from text: A look back and into the future. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 44(4), 1–36.
- Zamborlini, V., Hoekstra, R., Da Silveira, M., Pruski, C., Ten Teije, A., & Van Harmelen, F. (2016). Inferring recommendation interactions in clinical guidelines 1. *Semantic Web*, 7(4), 421–446.
- Zhou, L. (2007). Ontology learning: State of the art and open issues. *Information Technology and Management*, 8(3), 241–252.

Appendices

1 PDD Activities and Concepts

Activities Table

Table(5) describes the activities and subactivities along with their relationship with the deliverables as illustrated in the PDD diagram (figure 15).

Activity	Subactivity	Description
Target Guideline Preparation	Identify relevant guideline	Identify the target MEDICAL GUIDELINE from different medical authorities (e.g., NHG, FMS).
	Prepare guideline for knowledge extraction	Including translation (if necessary), text scraping, and text extraction.
Concepts Extraction	Identify relevant sections	Identifying the RELEVANT SECTIONS of the guideline including sections describing symptoms, physical examination, and treatment plans. Sections dealing with research background, differential diagnosis, or advice for the physician on how to diagnose are not relevant as they would not affect the conversation nor the resulting report.
	Extract potential concepts	Identify and extract POTENTIAL CONCEPTS (including nouns and noun phrases) from the RELEVANT SECTIONS either manually (as in this research) or automatically (in future research).
Patient Anatomy Graph Construction	Map potential concepts to SNOMED CT anatomy hierarchy	POTENTIAL CONCEPTS that are relevant to the human anatomy ontology are to be identified by mapping concepts to the human anatomy hierarchy in the SNOMED CT. The hierarchy path is: SNOMED CT concept \Rightarrow Body structure \Rightarrow Anatomical or acquired body structure.
	Identify SNOMED CT subtype relationships	From the <i>details</i> of the identified SNOMED CT concepts, identify the SUBTYPE RELATIONSHIPS to link ANATOMICAL STRUCTURES with their parents (The SNOMED CT attribute is : Is a (attribute) - SCTID: 116680003).
	Construct relevant anatomical structures hierarchy	Build the hierarchy of ANATOMICAL STRUCTURES using the SUBTYPE RELATIONSHIPS.

Activity	Subactivity	Description
	Expand the anatomical structures hierarchy to bodyStructure	<p>As the concepts identified from the medical guidelines will only include the anatomy directly related to the condition at hand, expand the ANATOMICAL STRUCTURES HIERARCHY upwards to the root concept of bodyStructure (SNOMED CT concept: Body structure (body structure) - SCTID: 123037004). For example, the path for the external auditory canal would be: Body structure ⇒ Anatomical or acquired body structure ⇒ Anatomical structure ⇒ Body organ structure ⇒ Organ part ⇒ Ear part ⇒ External ear structure ⇒ External ear part ⇒ External auditory canal structure ⇒ Entire external auditory canal.</p> <p>(Note that the anatomical structures described in this document and depicted in the WebVOWL graphs are shortened for the sake of brevity; however, the actual system should contain the human anatomy without abbreviation).</p>
	Map potential concepts to SNOMED CT functions hierarchy	To detect the ANATOMICAL FUNCTIONS, the concepts extracted from the guideline are to be mapped to the functions hierarchy of SNOMED CT (Function (observable entity) - SCTID: 246464006) .
	Assign functions to relevant anatomical structures	SNOMED CT does not provide a way to directly map an ANATOMICAL FUNCTION to the relevant ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE. This mapping is performed manually in this research; however there is a need in future research to find a way to derive explicit mappings (e.g., Ear(anatomicalStructure) , hasFunction, hearing(anatomicalFunction)).
	Formulate PAG triples	Formalize the binary relationships between two anatomical units in the form of a triple <subject, predicate, object>.
	Construct PAG ontology	Construct the PAG ONTOLOGY by combining the triples and adding additional ontology components including class definitions and OWL object-Property definitions.

Activity	Subactivity	Description
Patient Symptoms Graph Construction	Identify concepts in relevant guidelines symptoms section(s)	Identify concepts in all the sections in the guideline that contain abnormalities and complaints perceived and reported by the patient. The sections will vary between different MEDICAL GUIDELINES and different medical authorities. In the NHG guidelines, they include anamnesis (medical history) and physical examination.
	Exclude concepts not in SNOMED CT findings and disorders	Map the concepts from the RELEVANT SECTIONS of the MEDICAL GUIDELINES to the SNOMED CT hierarchies containing potential symptoms (findings and disorders) to exclude irrelevant concepts.
	Assign symptoms to relevant anatomical units	In most cases, the SNOMED CT provides a link between the SYMPTOM and the relevant ANATOMICAL UNIT using the attribute: Finding site (attribute) - SCTID: 363698007. Use that SNOMED CT attribute to establish the link.
	Formulate PSG triples	Formalize the binary relationships between ANATOMICAL UNITS and their SYMPTOMS in the form of a triple <subject, predicate, object>.
	Construct PSG ontology	Construct the PSG ONTOLOGY by combining the triples and adding additional ontology components including class definitions and OWL objectProperty definitions.
Patient Observations Graph Construction	Identify concepts in relevant guidelines observations section(s)	Identify concepts in all the sections in the guideline that contain abnormalities observed by the physician. The sections will vary between different MEDICAL GUIDELINES and different medical authorities. In the NHG guidelines, they include anamnesis and physical examination.
	Exclude concepts not in SNOMED CT findings and disorders	Map the concepts from the relevant sections of the MEDICAL GUIDELINES to the SNOMED CT hierarchies containing potential observations (findings and disorders, the same hierarchies containing SYMPTOMS) to exclude irrelevant concepts.

Activity	Subactivity	Description
	Assign observations to relevant anatomical units	As in the SYMPTOMS case, the SNOMED CT provides a link between the OBSERVATION and the relevant ANATOMICAL UNIT using the attribute: Finding site (attribute) - SCTID: 363698007. Use the SNOMED CT to establish the link.
	Formulate POG triples	Formalize the binary relationships between ANATOMICAL UNITS and their OBSERVATIONS in the form of a triple <subject, predicate, object>.
	Construct POG ontology	Construct the POG ONTOLOGY by combining the triples and adding additional ontology components including class definitions and OWL object-Property definitions.
Patient Diagnosis Graph Construction	Assign symptoms to the guideline diagnosis	As the guideline discusses a specific medical disorder or disease, define it as the diagnosis and assign it to the SYMPTOMS.
	Assign observations to the guideline diagnosis	As the guideline discusses a specific medical disorder or disease, define it as the diagnosis and assign it to the relevant OBSERVATIONS.
	Construct PDG ontology	Construct the PDG ONTOLOGY by combining the triples from the previous two subactivities and adding additional ontology components including class definitions and OWL objectProperty definitions.
Patient Treatment Graph Construction	Identify concepts in relevant guidelines treatments section(s)	Identify concepts in all the sections in the MEDICAL GUIDELINES that contain treatment options. The sections will vary between different guidelines and different medical authorities. In the NHG guidelines, they include non-drug treatment, pharmacological treatment, consultation and referral.
	Exclude concepts not in SNOMED CT procedure, dose form, and physical object	Map the concepts from the relevant sections of the MEDICAL GUIDELINES to the SNOMED CT hierarchies containing potential TREATMENTS (procedure, substance, dose form, and physical object) to exclude irrelevant concepts.

Activity	Subactivity	Description
	Assign treatment to the guideline diagnosis	As the guideline discusses a specific medical disorder or disease, assign it to the relevant TREATMENTS.
	Construct PTG ontology	Construct the PTG ONTOLOGY by combining the triples from the previous subactivity and adding additional ontology components including class definitions and OWL objectProperty definitions.
Patient Medical Graph Finalization	Add prefixes	Combine the previously constructed (sub) ontologies and add prefix definitions to complete the PMG ONTOLOGY.
	Confirm lack of disjoint concepts	As a validation step, confirm that all concepts of the ontology are joined to other concepts. For example, that no SYMPTOM or OBSERVATION is lacking a relationship to an ANATOMICAL UNIT.
	Add synonyms	As discussed in details in subsection 4.3, the inclusion of synonyms is an important consideration that is partly covered in manually constructed ontologies but should be fully studied when automating the process. In this activity, add synonyms from the SNOMED CT concepts descriptors to all concepts of the ontology.

Table 5: PDD Process Activities

Concepts Table

Table (6) describes the deliverables in the form of PDD concepts, as well as references to these concepts in the literature (when applicable). The formal definitions of the concepts related to the PMG are detailed in chapter 3.

Concept	Description
MEDICAL GUIDELINE	A MEDICAL GUIDELINE is a digital document with procedural instructions for executing an anamnesis, diagnosis and treatment in care provisions that aims to improve the quality of care, increase the patient’s health and well-being, and support medical decision-making. It is based on systematic summaries of scientific research, the considerations of various care options and is supplemented with the expertise and experience of care professionals.
RELEVANT SECTION	A RELEVANT SECTION of the MEDICAL GUIDELINE is a section directly providing information to be used in constructing and populating the ontology and the related knowledge graph used for the automated conversation summarization system. The relevant information include the names of the concerned anatomical units, potential symptoms and observations, and recommended treatments. Sections providing research background or instructions for the physician that would not be included in the consultation report are irrelevant.
POTENTIAL CONCEPT	A noun or noun phrase used to identify a relevant class in the ontology. A POTENTIAL CONCEPT is filtered in later stages against the SNOMED CT terminology to identify relevant concepts to the construction of the ontology.
ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE	A physical anatomical entity or a physical object that can consist of parts that are themselves anatomical structures (Rosse et al., 1998). For example, the ear and its parts (e.g., ear canal, eardrum, pinna) are all ANATOMICAL STRUCTURES.
SUBTYPE RELATIONSHIP	The relationship that relates a concept to its more generic parent concept(s) in the SNOMED CT hierarchy.
ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE HIERARCHY	A hierarchy of all the relevant ANATOMICAL STRUCTURES and the SUBTYPE RELATIONSHIPS between them.
ANATOMICAL FUNCTION	A task performed by one or a group of ANATOMICAL STRUCTURES (Rosse et al., 1998).

Concept	Description
ANATOMICAL UNIT	An ANATOMICAL UNIT concept encompasses both ANATOMICAL STRUCTURES and ANATOMICAL FUNCTIONS (Rosse & Mejino Jr, 2003).
ANATOMICAL UNITS HIERARCHY	A hierarchy of anatomical units, where an anatomical units is a component of the human anatomy that can have SYMPTOMS, OBSERVATIONS, diagnosis, or TREATMENTS. Anatomical units, in this definition, encompass both anatomical structures and functions .
PAG TRIPLE	A three-parts representation of the binary relationship between two concepts of the human anatomy; a triple takes the form <subject, predicate, object>.
PAG ONTOLOGY	An ontology depicting all the human anatomical structures and functions.
SYMPTOM	A subjective abnormality that the patient perceives and reports (LeBlond et al., 2015).
PSG TRIPLE	A three-parts representation of the binary relationship between a concept representing and ANATOMICAL UNIT and a SYMPTOM it exhibits.
PSG ONTOLOGY	An ontology representing all the complaints and anomalies reported by the patient.
OBSERVATION	An objective abnormality observed by the physician (LeBlond et al., 2015).
POG TRIPLE	A three-parts representation of the binary relationship between a concept representing and ANATOMICAL UNIT and an OBSERVATION it exhibits.
POG ONTOLOGY	An ontology representing all the observations made by the physician about the patient's condition.
SYMPTOM-DIAGNOSIS TRIPLE	A triple representing the relationship between a SYMPTOM and the diagnosis (topic of the guideline). The diagnosis is a condition or disease identified by the physician based on the SYMPTOMS and OBSERVATIONS.
OBSERVATION-DIAGNOSIS TRIPLE	A triple representing the relationship between an OBSERVATION and the diagnosis (topic of the guideline).
PDG ONTOLOGY	An ontology depicting the diagnosis of the patient's condition.

Concept	Description
TREATMENT	A TREATMENT encompasses any physician's prescription, including medications, instructions for the patient to follow, referral to a specialist, further tests, or any other procedure.
PTG TRIPLE	A three-parts representation of the binary relationship between a diagnosis and its TREATMENT.
PTG ONTOLOGY	An ontology describing all the TREATMENTS prescribed by the physician, including medications, instructions, referrals, or additional medical tests.
PMG ONTOLOGY	An all-encompassing ontology representing the patient's ANATOMICAL UNITS and SYMPTOMS and the physician's OBSERVATIONS, diagnosis and prescribed TREATMENTS.

Table 6: PDD Deliverable Concepts

2 Otitis Externa Ontology

Applying the procedure outlined in the Process-Deliverable Diagram (chapter 4) to the NHG guidelines of the running example condition of Otitis Externa provides the following ontology.

```
@prefix c2r: <https://sites.google.com/view/care2report/> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .

c2r:externalAuditoryCanal a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfExternalEar rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:externalAuditoryCanal;
    rdfs:range c2r:externalEarStructure.
c2r:earCanal a owl:Class.
owl:sameAsCanal rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "sameAs"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:earCanal;
    rdfs:range c2r:externalAuditoryCanal.
c2r:pinna a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfExternalEar rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:pinna;
    rdfs:range c2r:externalEarStructure.
c2r:earCanal a owl:Class.
owl:sameAsPinna rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "sameAs"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:auricle;
    rdfs:range c2r:pinna.
c2r:externalEarStructure a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfEar rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:externalEarStructure;
    rdfs:range c2r:earStructure.
c2r:tympanicMembraneStructure a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfMiddleEar rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:tympanicMembraneStructure;
    rdfs:range c2r:middleEarStructure.
c2r:earDrum a owl:Class.
```

```

owl:sameAsMembrane rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "sameAs"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:earDrum;
  rdfs:range c2r:tympanicMembraneStructure.
c2r:middleEarStructure a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfEar rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:middleEarStructure;
  rdfs:range c2r:earStructure.
c2r:earStructure a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfHeadandNeck rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:earStructure;
  rdfs:range c2r:structureOfHeadAndNeck.
c2r:hearing a owl:Class.
c2r:hasFunctionHearing rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasFunction"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:earStructure;
  rdfs:range c2r:hearing.
c2r:structureOfHeadAndNeck a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfUpperBody rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:structureOfHeadAndNeck;
  rdfs:range c2r:upperBodyStructure.
c2r:upperBodyStructure a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfBody rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:upperBodyStructure;
  rdfs:range c2r:bodyStructure.
c2r:patient a owl:Class.
c2r:bodyStructure a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfPatient rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:bodyStructure;
  rdfs:range c2r:patient.
c2r:canalhasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:externalAuditoryCanal;
  rdfs:range c2r:pain.
c2r:canalhasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;

```

```

    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:externalAuditoryCanal;
    rdfs:range c2r:itching.
c2r:canalhasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:externalAuditoryCanal;
    rdfs:range c2r:drinage.
c2r:hearinghasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:hearing;
    rdfs:range c2r:hearingLoss.
c2r:canalhasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:externalAuditoryCanal;
    rdfs:range c2r:scarring.
c2r:canalhasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:externalAuditoryCanal;
    rdfs:range c2r:swelling.
c2r:canalhasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:externalAuditoryCanal;
    rdfs:range c2r:flaking.
c2r:canalhasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:externalAuditoryCanal;
    rdfs:range c2r:redness.
c2r:earDrumhasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:tympanicMembraneStructure;
    rdfs:range c2r:rapture.
c2r:otitisExterna a owl:Class.
c2r:diagnosedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "diagnosedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:otitisExterna.
c2r:earCleaning a owl:Class.
c2r:treatedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "treatedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;

```

```
    rdfs:range c2r:earCleaning.
c2r:hasTreatment rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasTreatment"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:otitisExterna;
    rdfs:range c2r:earCleaning.
c2r:earDrops a owl:Class.
c2r:treatedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "treatedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:earDrops.
c2r:hasTreatment rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasTreatment"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:otitisExterna;
    rdfs:range c2r:earDrops.
c2r:referral a owl:Class.
c2r:treatedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "treatedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:referral.
c2r:hasTreatment rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasTreatment"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:otitisExterna;
    rdfs:range c2r:referral.
```

3 Ontology and WebVOWL visualization of Acute Rhinosinusitis

Acute Rhinosinusitis, also known as Acute sinusitis, is a short-term inflammation of the membranes that line the nose and surrounding sinuses. The NHG guidelines are used to construct the ontology of this disorder and the resulting WebVOWL visualization.

Acute Rhinosinusitis Ontology

```
@prefix c2r: <https://sites.google.com/view/care2report/> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
```

```
c2r:eyeLid a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfEye rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:eyeLid;
  rdfs:range c2r:eye.
c2r:eye a owl:Class.
c2r:head a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfHead rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:eye;
  rdfs:range c2r:head.
c2r:foreHead a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfHead rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:foreHead;
  rdfs:range c2r:head.
c2r:ear a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfHead rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:ear;
  rdfs:range c2r:head.
c2r:face a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfHead rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:face;
  rdfs:range c2r:head.
c2r:nose a owl:Class.
```

```

c2r:isPartOfFace rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:nose;
  rdfs:range c2r:face.
c2r:mouth a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfHead rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:mouth;
  rdfs:range c2r:head.
c2r:teeth a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfOral rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:teeth;
  rdfs:range c2r:oralSoftTissue.
c2r:oralSoftTissue a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfMouth rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:oralSoftTissue;
  rdfs:range c2r:mouth.
c2r:throat a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfNeck rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:throat;
  rdfs:range c2r:neck.
c2r:head a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfBody rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:head;
  rdfs:range c2r:bodyStructure.
c2r:neck a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfBody rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:neck;
  rdfs:range c2r:bodyStructure.
c2r:bodyStructure a owl:Class.
c2r:patient a owl:Class.
c2r:isPartOfPatient rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "isPartOf"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:bodyStructure;
  rdfs:range c2r:patient.

```

```

c2r:mastication a owl:Class.
c2r:MouthhasFunction rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasFunction"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:mouth;
    rdfs:range c2r:mastication.
c2r:chewing a owl:Class.
owl:sameAsMastication rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "sameAs"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:chewing;
    rdfs:range c2r:mastication.
c2r:rhinorrhoea a owl:Class.
c2r:NosehasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:nose;
    rdfs:range c2r:rhinorrhoea.
c2r:runnyNose a owl:Class.
owl:sameAsRhinorrhoea rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "sameAs"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:runnyNose;
    rdfs:range c2r:rhinorrhoea.
c2r:decreasedSenseOfSmell a owl:Class.
c2r:NosehasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:nose;
    rdfs:range c2r:decreasedSenseOfSmell.
c2r:sneeze a owl:Class.
c2r:NosehasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:nose;
    rdfs:range c2r:sneeze.
c2r:soreThroat a owl:Class.
c2r:ThroathasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:throat;
    rdfs:range c2r:soreThroat.
c2r:pain a owl:Class.
c2r:FacehasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:face;
    rdfs:range c2r:pain.

```

```

c2r:EyehasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:eye;
  rdfs:range c2r:pain.
c2r:MasticationhasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:mastication;
  rdfs:range c2r:pain.
c2r:headache a owl:Class.
c2r:HeadhasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:head;
  rdfs:range c2r:headache.
c2r:toothache a owl:Class.
c2r:TeethhasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:teeth;
  rdfs:range c2r:toothache.
c2r:fever a owl:Class.
c2r:PatienthasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
  rdfs:range c2r:fever.
c2r:irritability a owl:Class.
c2r:PatienthasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
  rdfs:range c2r:irritability.
c2r:restlessness a owl:Class.
c2r:PatienthasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
  rdfs:range c2r:restlessness.
c2r:drowsiness a owl:Class.
c2r:PatienthasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
  rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
  rdfs:range c2r:drowsiness.
c2r:apathy a owl:Class.
c2r:PatienthasSymptom rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;

```

```

    rdfs:label "hasSymptom"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:apathy.
c2r:edema a owl:Class.
c2r:EyeLidhasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:eyeLid;
    rdfs:range c2r:edema.
c2r:redness a owl:Class.
c2r:EyeLidhasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:eyeLid;
    rdfs:range c2r:redness.
c2r:swelling a owl:Class.
c2r:foreHeadhasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:foreHead;
    rdfs:range c2r:swelling.
c2r:exophthalmia a owl:Class.
c2r:eyehasObservation rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "hasObservation"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:eye;
    rdfs:range c2r:exophthalmia.
c2r:eyeBulging a owl:Class.
owl:sameAsexophthalmia rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "sameAs"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:eyeBulging;
    rdfs:range c2r:exophthalmia.
c2r:acuteRhinosinusitis a owl:Class.
c2r:diagnosedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "diagnosedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:acuteRhinosinusitis.
c2r:eyeBulging a owl:Class.
owl:sameAsacuteRhinosinusitis rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "sameAs"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:acuteSinusitis;
    rdfs:range c2r:acuteRhinosinusitis.
c2r:nasalDrops a owl:Class.
c2r:treatedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;

```

```

    rdfs:label "treatedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:nasalDrops.
c2r:nasalSpray a owl:Class.
c2r:treatedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "treatedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:nasalSpray.
c2r:analgesic a owl:Class.
c2r:treatedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "treatedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:analgesic.
c2r:painKiller a owl:Class.
owl:sameAsanalgesic rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "sameAs"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:painKiller;
    rdfs:range c2r:analgesic.
c2r:antibiotic a owl:Class.
c2r:treatedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "treatedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:antibiotic.
c2r:nasalCorticosteroid a owl:Class.
c2r:treatedWith rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
    rdfs:label "treatedWith"@en;
    rdfs:domain c2r:patient;
    rdfs:range c2r:nasalCorticosteroid.

```

Acute Rhinosinusitis WebVOWL Visualization

Figure (17) depicts the WebVOWL representation of the condition guidelines.⁴

⁴ A clearer SVG version of the figure can be accessed [here](#).

A Framework for Ontology Creation from Medical Guidelines

Omar ElAssy^[0000-0001-6202-2465], Rik de Vendt^[0000-0002-2131-0425], Fabiano Dalpiaz^[0000-0003-4480-3887], and Sjaak Brinkkemper^[0000-0002-2977-8911]

Dept. of Information and Computing Sciences, Utrecht University, The Netherlands
{o.omarihabelsayedelassy, r.devendt, s.brinkkemper, f.dalpiaz@uu.nl}@uu.nl

Abstract. The automated capturing and summarisation of medical consultations can save time and cost. They are structured conversations that broadly follow a systematic examination of predefined observations and symptoms to diagnose and treat well-defined conditions affecting fixed human anatomy. However, the advancement and wide adoption of automated conversation summarization systems depend on the availability of machine-processable representation of medical knowledge. This paper aims to formalize the representation of medical guidelines by developing a framework to systematically construct ontologies from the human anatomy and medical guidelines. The Systematized Nomenclature Of Medicine - Clinical Terminology (SNOMED CT) and medical guidelines from a Dutch medical authority are used to develop a notational representation for the target ontologies in the form of a Patient Medical Graph (PMG) and a procedural method to develop such ontologies expressed in the form of a Process-Deliverable Diagram (PDD) model. An ontology of the medical condition of ear canal inflammation (Otitis Externa) is created and visualized to validate the framework.

Keywords: Ontology learning · knowledge extraction · medical knowledge representation · Patient Medical Graph · Care2Report.

1 Introduction

The automated summarization of conversations have the potential to save time and cost, especially in domains where dialogues are structured based on predefined guidelines. Medical consultations are a prime example as they broadly follow a systematic examination of predefined symptoms and observations to diagnose and treat well-defined conditions affecting fixed human anatomy. The expanding potential of the automated conversation summarization systems in the medical domain and other fields depends on the readiness of the structured representations of domain-specific knowledge in a machine-processable format. The rule-based conversations summarization grants explainability unachievable in machine learning approaches, and ontologies can efficiently represent domain guidelines in such rule-based applications.

Gruber [10] defined an ontology as the explicit specification of a conceptualization. It is a formal description of the concepts in a domain and the relationships between these concepts. In the context of conversation summarization, the ontology represents the diverse and primarily textual domain knowledge (e.g., human anatomy and medical guidelines) in a machine-processable fabric of concepts and relationships. Manually building a domain ontology is time-consuming and error-prone; thus, it should be carried out using systematic ontology learning: constructing and integrating a machine-readable semantic-rich ontology (semi-)automatically [28].

However, the development of tools and techniques for ontology learning primarily aims to extract knowledge from general data corpora as it was, and still is, driven by the necessity of linking either openly available data (e.g., DBpedia [14]) or corporate-specific business data (e.g. Google Knowledge Graph [11]). Therefore, more research is needed to develop a framework to enable the systematic representation of domain guidelines in machine-processable ontologies. This paper develops a framework for ontologies in the medical domain to support the development and expansion of the automated conversation summarization system Care2Report [16].

The Care2Report system proposed an approach to reduce the administrative burden in medical care by automating the capturing, transcription, and report generation of medical consultations [16]. The summarization pipeline relies on an ontology embodying the field’s vocabulary and guidelines that act as the structured container to be filled with the multimodal information from the medical consultation. The information extracted from the conversation populates the ontology to generate the rule-adhering report that the physician checks before uploading to the Electronic Medical Records system (EMR) [17]. This paper investigates elements of the second stage of the Care2Report pipeline, formal representation (figure 1). The multimodal data recorded and processed during the medical consultation is formally expressed using a knowledge representation formalism to allow further analysis in later stages.

The medical domain knowledge is assembled by analyzing the human anatomy and medical terminologies provided by the Systematized Nomenclature Of Medicine - Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) [24]; and the medical guidelines provided by the Dutch College of General Practitioners (Nederlands Huisartsen Genootschap - NHG) [18]. The outcome consists of the two perspectives of the ontology learning framework: the notational side represented by the Patient Medical Graph (PMG), and the procedural method expressed in a Process-Deliverable Diagram (PDD) model. The design science research cycle, as described by Wieringa [27], is fitting to answer the research question: **How to systematically construct ontologies from the human anatomy and medical guidelines?**

Fig. 1: Stages of the Care2Report Pipeline [6]

2 Guidelines and Nomenclature in Medical Informatics

2.1 Medical Guidelines

A medical guideline is a digital document with definitions and procedural instructions for executing an anamnesis, diagnosis and treatment in care provisions that aim to advance care quality, improve the patient’s health and well-being, and support medical decision-making. It is based on systematic summaries of scientific research, the considerations of various care options, and care professionals’ expertise. Numerous international and national medical authorities publish and maintain medical guidelines.

In the Netherlands, both the Dutch College of General Practitioners (Nederlands Huisartsen Genootschap - NHG) and the Dutch Federation of Medical Specialists (Federatie Medisch Specialisten - FMS) publish guidelines in several specializations [18, 8]. The guidelines include sections about prognosis, common causes and background, physical examination and diagnosis guidelines, treatment policy, consultations and referral guidelines (if any), and control and future patient check-ups.

The symptoms and observations indicating a condition and the treatments recommended for such condition by the guidelines are relevant to the construction and population of the Patient Medical Graph (PMG) and the related ontologies, as will be detailed in the coming sections. As the PMG (and ultimately the resulting consultation report) aims to represent the conversation between the patient and the physician rather than support the physician’s decision making,

the reasoning behind which treatment to choose is beyond our scope. Therefore, the PMG and its accompanying ontology and knowledge base should contain all treatment possibilities as options, while the physician’s discretion will decide which ones to use.

2.2 Medical Nomenclature: SNOMED CT

The Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine - Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) is currently the world’s most extensive clinical terminology system [4]. This paper uses SNOMED CT as an ontology source representing human anatomy and terminology hierarchy to identify relevant medical concepts from all the potential concepts in the textual medical guidelines. The terminology structure is in hierarchical formations of concepts defined and connected to each other by relationships, with identifiers for machine use and descriptors for human readability (figure 2).

Fig. 2: SNOMED CT Design [24]

The top node of the SNOMED CT hierarchy is occupied by the root concept *SNOMED CT concept*, and nineteen direct subtypes of it are the *top level concepts* that provide the structure of the SNOMED CT (figure 2). Thus, different conditions and medical consultations will use a subset of the available concept hierarchies.

3 Patient Medical Graph

The Patient Medical Graph (PMG) is an all-encompassing knowledge graph representing the patient’s anatomy and symptoms and the physician’s observations, diagnosis and prescribed treatments, where symptoms are subjective abnormalities that the patient perceives, while observations are objective abnormalities detected by the physician [13]. It consists of five subgraphs, the Patient Anatomy Graph (PAG) depicting all the human anatomical structures and functions, the Patient Symptoms Graph (PSG) representing all the complaints and anomalies (symptoms) reported by the patient, the Patient Observations Graph (POG) representing all the observations made by the physician about the patient’s condition, the Patient Diagnosis Graph (PDG) describing the physician’s diagnosis of the patient’s condition, and finally the Patient Treatment Graph (PTG) describing all the treatments prescribed by the physician, including medications, instructions, referrals, or additional medical tests.

3.1 Patient Anatomy Graph

The Patient Anatomy Graph (PAG) is the foundation for the knowledge representation in the PMG. The PAG can be built based on existing resources like the Foundational Model of Anatomy [22], or it can utilize an existing hierarchical terminology structure like SNOMED CT, as in this research. Within the SNOMED CT hierarchies, the human anatomy is represented in one section: *SNOMED CT concept* ⇒ *Body structure* ⇒ *Anatomical or acquired body structure* [25]. Figure (3a) lays the meta-modelling foundation for the model used in the PAG where an anatomical unit is either an anatomical structure or a function [21]. Figure (3b) shows the reference PMG notation representation of the patient anatomy.

(a) Meta-model of the Patient Anatomy Graph

(b) Patient Anatomy Graph reference notations

Fig. 3: The Patient Anatomy Graph (PAG)

3.2 PMG Overall structure

The medical report produced by the automated conversation summarization system Care2Report to upload into the EMR follows a predefined structure of four sections: subjective (what the patient reports), objective (what the physician identifies), evaluation (assessment and diagnosis), and plan for treatment and follow up [5]. Following the same arrangement, the PMG consists of a composite of four subgraphs reflecting the four aspects of reporting and a fifth foundational subgraph for human anatomy.

Each of the five subgraphs (anatomy, symptoms, observations, diagnosis, and treatment) builds on the previous one(s) to include further knowledge into the resulting PMG (figure 4). The PMG provides the notational aspect of the ontology development framework.

(a) Meta-model of the Patient Medical Graph

(b) Patient Medical Graph reference notations

Fig. 4: The Patient Medical Graph (PMG)

The PMG and its instantiation with information from specific consultation provide a graphical representation of ontology-based knowledge where every two concepts and the relationship between them form a triple. Examples of such triples are introduced in the coming sections.

4 Formalization of the PMG

The structure and the interaction between the various subgraphs are relatively intuitive for simple conditions concerning comparatively simple body structures. However, adding the complete human anatomy and the guidelines from several medical authorities can make the graphs less intuitive to understand and communicate. Therefore, it is essential to introduce formal descriptions of the subgraphs and their components; this section introduces a few of these descriptions. Formally defining the PMG and its subgraphs requires the definition of the following sets:

Set	Description
B	all anatomical structures of the body.
F	all anatomical functions of the body.
A	all anatomical units ($A = B \cup F$).
P	all patients (A patient is also an anatomical unit: $P \subset A$).
S	all medical symptoms (reported by the patient).
O	all medical observations (observed by the physician).
V	all possible values to be assigned to symptoms $s \in S$ or observations $o \in O$.
D	all medical diagnoses.
E	all explicit diagnoses.
I	all implicit diagnoses.
T	all medical treatments.

The formal definitions of the subgraphs comprising the PMG are the following:

Graph	Vertices	Edges
PAG	$A = B \cup F$	$\{(b_1, b_2) \mid b_1, b_2 \in B \wedge b_1 \text{ is a direct anatomical sub-part of } b_2$ \vee $(b, f) \mid b \in B \wedge f \in F \wedge b \text{ has an anatomical function } f\}$.
PSG	$A \cup S \cup V$	$\{(a, s), (s, v) \mid a \in A \wedge s \in S \wedge v \in V\}$ i.e., all symptoms.
POG	$A \cup O \cup V$	$\{(a, o), (o, v) \mid a \in A \wedge o \in O \wedge v \in V\}$ i.e., all observations.
PDG	$P \cup D$	$\{(p, d) \mid p \in P \wedge d \in D\}$ i.e., all the diagnoses of patient p .
PTG	$P \cup T$	$\{(p, t) \mid p \in P \wedge t \in T\}$ i.e., all the treatments of patient p .

And as discussed before, the PMG is an all-encompassing knowledge graph representing the patient's anatomy and symptoms and the physician's observations, diagnosis and treatments: $\text{PMG} = \text{PAG} \cup \text{PSG} \cup \text{POG} \cup \text{PDG} \cup \text{PTG}$.

Finally, some of the rules that need to be coded into the system to define the relationships between the entities in the different subgraphs are listed below, consulting domain experts is expected to add to this list:

1. Each anatomical structure (b) is a part of another anatomical structure (b) unless it is the complete body structure (b*).
 $\forall b_1 \exists b_2 : \text{isPartOf}(b_1, b_2) \quad b_1, b_2 \in B, \neg (b_1 = b^*)$
2. Each function (f) is assigned to one or more anatomical structure (b).
 $\forall f \exists b : \text{hasFunction}(b, f) \quad b \in B, f \in F$
3. Each symptom (s) is associated with one or more anatomical unit (a).
 $\forall s \exists a : \text{hasSymptom}(a, s) \quad s \in S, a \in A$
4. Each observation (o) is associated with one or more anatomical unit (a).
 $\forall o \exists a : \text{hasObservation}(a, o) \quad o \in O, a \in A$
5. A patient (p) is diagnosed with a diagnosis (d).
 $\forall p \exists d : \text{diagnosedWith}(p, d) \quad p \in P, d \in D$
6. A patient (p) is treated with a treatment (t). A treatment encompasses any physician's prescription, including medications, instructions for the patient to follow, referral to a specialist, further tests, or any other procedure.
 $\forall p \exists t : \text{treatedWith}(p, t) \quad p \in P, t \in T$
7. An explicit diagnosis (e) is associated with a symptom (s) or an observation (o).
 $\forall e \exists s \exists o : \text{associatedWith}(s, e) \vee \text{associatedWith}(o, e)$
 $e \in E, s \in S, o \in O$
8. An implicit diagnosis is not explicit. That is, an implicit diagnosis (i) is neither associated with a symptom (s) nor an observation (o).
 $\forall i \forall e : \neg (i = e) \quad i \in I, e \in E$

5 Method for Systematic Creation of Medical Ontologies

While the previous section introduced the PMG notations representing the medical guidelines ontology, this section introduces the procedural method perspective outlined in a Process-Deliverable Diagram (PDD) model. The PDD illustrates the activities and artefacts of a specific process [26]. The model depicts the activities on the left-hand side of the PDD diagram using UML activity diagram notations, while the deliverables are on the right-hand side of the diagram using UML class diagram notations [20]. The model emphasizes the relationships between the activities and their deliverables by connecting them with dotted arrows across the diagram [26].

5.1 Ontology Creation PDD

Figure(5) shows the used PDD, in which the process is broken down into eight main activities. For simplicity, activities three to seven are illustrated (and manually performed) sequentially; however, they can also be executed in parallel.

Fig. 5: PDD of the Ontology Creation Process

1. **Target guideline preparation:**The guideline of the medical condition is selected from the medical authority’s website, translated (if necessary), scraped, and prepared for the following concept extraction activity.

2. **Concept extraction:** The relevant sections of the guidelines are identified, including sections describing symptoms, physical examination, and treatment plans. As nouns are the natural language representation of things, ideas and notions, they identify the concepts to be extracted (rather than other parts of speech). Thus, the potential concepts to extract are all nouns and noun phrases in the relevant sections that will later be mapped against the SNOMED CT to identify the constituent concepts of the ontology (e.g., anatomical units, symptoms, observations, and treatments). Some potential concepts will not be used in the ontology as they represent general nouns used in the text.
3. **Patient Anatomy Graph (PAG) construction:** The guideline concepts corresponding to SNOME CT *anatomical concepts* are identified and converted into a hierarchy from which the PAG ontology is constructed.
4. **Patient Symptoms Graph (PSG) construction:** The concepts identified in the medical guideline sections describing symptoms are mapped against the corresponding SNOMED CT hierarchies (*findings* and *disorders*) to build the PSG ontology.
5. **Patient Observations Graph (POG) construction:** Similar to the previous activity except dealing with physician observations instead of patient-described symptoms. Thus, the relevant guideline sections are different.
6. **Patient Diagnosis Graph (PDG) construction:** The medical condition or disease discussed in the guideline is the diagnosis associated with symptoms and observations to construct the PDG ontology.
7. **Patient Treatment Graph (PTG) construction:** The concepts identified in the treatment-related sections of the guideline are mapped against the corresponding SNOMED CT hierarchies (*procedure*, *substance*, *dose form*, and *physical object*) to build the PTG ontology.
8. **Patient Medical Graph Finalization:** All the previous subgraphs and the resultant sub ontologies are combined along with needed information (e.g., prefixes) to construct the complete PMG. This activity also includes checks to validity by confirming the lack of disjoint concepts.

5.2 A Detailed Look on Subgraphs Creation

Figure (6) expands the PAG construction activity to show the various subactivities and the resulting deliverables. The PDD activities constructing the remaining subgraphs follow the same general high-level pattern to build the relevant ontology based on the list of extracted potential concepts from the guidelines. Potential concepts are mapped at each stage to both the relevant sections of the guidelines (e.g., physical examination and treatment policy) and the relevant hierarchies of the SNOMED CT (e.g., findings and disorders). Thus, the concepts that show in both relevant modules are the appropriate candidate concepts for the ontology at hand (e.g., symptom concept, observation concept or treatment concept). For a detailed illustration of the complete PDD and a description of all the (sub)activities and concepts, refer to the technical report published July 2021.

Fig. 6: Patient Anatomy Graph (PAG) construction

6 Application on Otitis Externa

To illustrate the PMG notations and apply the derived procedure to create an ontology, we use the NHG guideline for the inflammation of the external ear canal known as Otitis Externa [19]. The condition is chosen as an example for the relative simplicity of the associated guidelines and the lack of complicated medical procedures, terminology, or differential diagnosis. Otitis Externa is an inflammation caused by a disturbance in the typical acidic environment of the ear canal and thus is usually associated with swimming. The symptoms reported by the patient may include ear pain, itching in the ear, fluid drainage from the ear, and hearing loss. In addition, the physician examines both the complaint-free ear and the affected ear for signs of scars, swelling, flaking, redness, and the state of the eardrum, among others [19].

Some symptoms (e.g., hearing loss) are not required for an Otitis Externa diagnosis, indicating that while the PMG and ontological representation of the condition should include it as a possible symptom, some specific consultations might have this symptom present while others do not. Also, the guidelines indicate that the physician should check the eardrum; however, Otitis Externa is not associated with any observations regarding the eardrum, suggesting that any observation of the eardrum (e.g., rupture) might indicate a different diagnosis. As for the treatment, the guideline recommends that the physician should instruct the patient on how to clean the infected ear properly, and prescribe ear drops. In addition, referral to a specialist is recommended if the condition does not improve promptly or if the patient is from a specific vulnerable group (e.g., elderly and diabetic).

As an example, we consider a fictitious consultation for an Otitis Externa patient suffering from ear pain (no indication of itching, fluid drainage, or hearing loss), and the examination shows swelling, redness, and skin flaking in the external ear canal. Figure (7a) represents the general PMG of the Otitis Externa

condition with indication of the guideline sections forming it, while figure (7b) is the consultation-specific PMG for the fictitious patient.

The PMG can be represented in triples for machine processing; for example, some of the triples portrayed in figure (7b) are explained below:

- The human anatomy is represented in a hierarchy of anatomical structures connected to their parent structures using *isPartOf* relationships. For example, $\langle \text{externalAuditoryCanal}, \text{isPartOf}, \text{ear} \rangle$.
- The second constituents of the PAG is the assignment of anatomical functions to the anatomical structures performing them as in $\langle \text{ear}, \text{hasFunction}, \text{hearing} \rangle$.
- The symptoms and observations triples comprise the PSG and the POG respectively. For example, the following three triples demonstrate a pain symptom: $\langle \text{externalAuditoryCanal}, \text{hasSymptom}, \text{symp_2} \rangle$, $\langle \text{symp_2}, \text{symptom}, \text{earPain} \rangle$, $\langle \text{symp_2}, \text{hasValue}, 7/10 \rangle$.
- And finally, the patient diagnosis and treatments are expressed in triples as in the following examples: $\langle \text{patient}, \text{diagnosedWith}, \text{OtitisExterna} \rangle$, $\langle \text{patient}, \text{treatedWith}, \text{earDrops} \rangle$.

Applying the procedure outlined in the PDD to the Otitis Externa condition produces the ontology visualized in figure (8) using the WebVOWL web application [15]. For conciseness, the ontology visualized does not contain the top-level classes (anatomy, symptom, observation, diagnosis, and treatment) and the *rdfs:subClassOf* relationship linking the other concepts to them. For the complete ontology construction process and the resulting ontology, refer to the technical report published July 2021.

The method was applied manually, which required substantial time investment. The full implementation potential of the Care2Report system relies on developing an automatic process to generate ontologies of all medical conditions using guidelines from various countries and in different languages. The ontology development relies on data from two sources: SNOMED CT, which can be directly transformed into an OWL ontology with relatively few steps; and the text-based medical guidelines that pose the real challenge for knowledge extraction and structuring to be tackled in future research.

(a) PMG of the Otitis Externa Condition

(b) Example PMG of an Otitis Externa patient

Fig. 7: Otitis Externa representation in PMG

Fig. 8: WebVOWL Visualization of the Otitis Externa Ontology

7 Conclusion

The paper aimed to create a framework for the systematic creation of medical ontologies from the SNOMED CT terminology and anatomical hierarchies, combined with the medical guidelines of different medical conditions. The resulting PMG provides a formalized notation, and the PDD provides a procedural guide to systematically create ontologies and enrich them by connecting new guidelines to the existing definitions of anatomy, symptoms, observations, and treatments; and adding more if the existing concepts are insufficient to represent the guideline fully.

However, more research is needed to validate the framework on guidelines of more complex and varying conditions. For example, the NHG guideline for "Non-traumatic knee complaints" details a method for differentiating between various similar conditions and thus does not follow the same divided sections typical in most of the NHG guidelines. Moreover, some guidelines only point the physician towards the tests and measurements to monitor without detailing the results or values to look for, presumably because the results are hard to detail in the text while the medical professionals understand them. For example, the guidelines advise performing an electrocardiogram (EKG) test in several cardiovascular conditions without detailing the expected outcomes. The Care2Report multi-modal input architecture [16] aims to eventually allow the integration of (some of) the measurement data, but an ontology to represent this knowledge still needs to be developed. Finally, more research is needed towards automating different (sub)activities to enable the efficient creation of complete ontologies of the human anatomy and medical guidelines from different medical authorities.

References

1. Ajami, S.: Use of speech-to-text technology for documentation by healthcare providers. *The National medical journal of India* **29**(3), 148 (2016)
2. Arndt, B.G. et al.: Tethered to the EHR: primary care physician workload assessment using EHR event log data and time-motion observations. *The Annals of Family Medicine* **15**(5), 419–426 (2017)
3. Babbott, S. et al.: Electronic medical records and physician stress in primary care: results from the MEMO Study. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* **21**(e1), e100–e106 (2014)
4. Bodenreider, O. et al.: Recent developments in clinical terminologies—SNOMED CT, LOINC, and RxNorm. *Yearbook of medical informatics* **27**(1), (2018)
5. Cameron, S., Turtle-Song, I.: Learning to write case notes using the SOAP format. *Journal of Counseling & Development* **80**(3), 286–292 (2002)
6. Care2Report - Mission, <https://sites.google.com/view/care2report/mission>. Last accessed 27 June 2021
7. Chiu, C.-C. et al.: Speech recognition for medical conversations. arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.07274 (2017)
8. Federatie Medisch Specialisten FMS - Richtlijnen (Guidelines of The Dutch Federation of Medical Specialists), <https://richtlijnendatabase.nl/>. Last accessed 27 June 2021

9. Friedberg, M.W. et al.: Factors affecting physician professional satisfaction and their implications for patient care, health systems, and health policy. *Rand health quarterly* **3**(4), (2014)
10. Gruber, T.R.: A translation approach to portable ontology specifications. *Knowledge acquisition* **5**(2), 199–220 (1993)
11. Introducing the Knowledge Graph: things, not strings, <https://blog.google/products/search/introducing-knowledge-graph-things-not/>. Last accessed 27 June 2021
12. Klann, J.G., Szolovits, P.: An intelligent listening framework for capturing encounter notes from a doctor-patient dialog. *BMC medical informatics and decision making* **9**(1), 1–10 (2009)
13. LeBlond, R.F.: *DeGowin’s diagnostic examination*. McGraw-Hill Education New York, NY (2015)
14. Lehmann, J. et al.: Dbpedia—a large-scale, multilingual knowledge base extracted from wikipedia. *Semantic web* **6**(2), 167–195 (2015)
15. Lohmann, S. et al.: Visualizing ontologies with VOWL. *Semantic Web* **7**(4), 99–419 (2016)
16. Maas, L. et al.: The Care2Report system: automated medical reporting as an integrated solution to reduce administrative burden in healthcare. In: *Proceedings of the 53rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pp. 3608–3617 (2020)
17. Molenaar, S. et al.: Medical dialogue summarization for automated reporting in healthcare. In: *The International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering*, pp 76–88, Springer (2020)
18. Nederlands Huisartsen Genootschap NHG - Richtlijnen (Guidelines of The Dutch College of General Practitioners), <https://richtlijnen.nhg.org/>. Last accessed 27 June 2021
19. NHG Otitis Externa Guidelines, <https://richtlijnen.nhg.org/standaarden/otitis-externa>. Last accessed 27 June 2021
20. Omg, MDA: Model Driven Architecture Guide Version 1.0.1. Object Management Group **62**, (2003)
21. Rosse, C. et al.: Motivation and organizational principles for the Digital Anatomist Symbolic Knowledge Base: an approach toward standards in anatomical knowledge representation. *J Am Med Inform Assoc* **5**, 17–40 (1998)
22. Rosse, C., Mejino Jr, J.L.: A reference ontology for biomedical informatics: the Foundational Model of Anatomy. *Journal of biomedical informatics* **36**(6), 478–500 (2003)
23. SNOMED CT 5-step briefing, <https://www.snomed.org/snomed-ct/five-step-briefing>. Last accessed 27 June 2021
24. SNOMED CT Basics, <https://confluence.ihtsdotools.org/display/DOCSTART/4.+SNOMED+CT+Basics>. Last accessed 27 June 2021
25. SNOMED CT Browser, <https://browser.ihtsdotools.org>. Last accessed 27 June 2021
26. van de Weerd, I., Brinkkemper, S.: Meta-modeling for situational analysis and design methods. In: *Handbook of research on modern systems analysis and design technologies and applications*, pp 35–54, IGI Global (2009)
27. Wieringa, R.J.: *Design science methodology for information systems and software engineering*. Springer (2014)
28. Zhou, L.: Ontology learning: state of the art and open issues. *Information Technology and Management* **8**(3), 241–252 (2007)